

HyDelta 4

WP3a – Defining gas quality tolerances in distribution grids and at network interfaces

D3a.2 Realistic hydrogen specifications in hydrogen distribution grids

Final version

Document summary

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Document history

Version	Date	Author	Affiliation	Summary of main changes
1	29-10-2025	Cas Bastiaanse, Martijn van Essen	DNV	First version
2	13-1-2026	Cas Bastiaanse, Martijn van Essen	DNV	Split version (this document contains only the technical gas quality part)
3	27-1-2026	Cas Bastiaanse, Martijn van Essen	DNV	Final version

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
RE	Restricted to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project partners including Expert Assessment Group External entity with whom a Non-Disclosure Agreement exists 	

Document review

Partner	Name
NBNL, Gasunie, Kiwa, DNV, TNO, NEC	HyDelta Supervisory Group

Tag (Choose only ONE):

Technology and Safety

- Activities (e.g. maintenance, purging etc.)
- Assets
- Digitalisation
- End use
- Gas network
- QRA

Value chains

Gas Quality

- Admixing
- Gas Quality
- Odourisation

Social aspects

- Conversion (of the distribution network)
- Education
- Social

System and Economy

- Business Development
- Production and supply

Executive summary

Key Takeaways:

- If the hydrogen from the Hydrogen Network Netherlands is already contaminated, it could be difficult for some sections of a repurposed distribution network to adhere to the 99.5% purity level set in the EZK-proposed (KGG) hydrogen specification in distribution grids (especially under <1 bar).
 - If the purity level specification (the >99.5 vol% H₂) is relaxed under a specific distribution pressure (e.g. somewhere between 1-4 bar), and the Wobbe index limit is used instead, some more contamination can be tolerated. This would facilitate distribution in re-used pipelines or lower pressure pipelines.
 - The amount of contamination tolerable by the installed combustion equipment is determined by the type of contamination. The Wobbe Index can be used to evaluate this.
 - Since end-users of pipelines under ~1 bar are predominately combustion end-users, the Wobbe Index is a more relevant limit than the purity specification alone.
 - However, the rate of change in hydrogen purity should be limited. Specific hazardous contaminants (ammonia etc.) should always be limited, regardless of the pressure level.
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In the Dutch natural gas network, strict quality limits are encoded in law so that customers know what to expect. For hydrogen, such specifications do not yet exist, creating uncertainty for producers, network operators, and end-users. A proposed Dutch national 99.5% purity specification (the *EZK-specification*) has been proposed (but not yet included in the *Energiewet* or adopted by the network operator) for the developing Hydrogen Network Netherlands and distribution networks.

In contrast to the isolated and controlled high-pressure transmission system, distribution grids are more decentralized and diverse and therefore more prone to impurities through normal operations. Additionally, unforeseen incidents can occur. This work package addresses whether the 99.5% hydrogen purity (with regulated odorization) can also be guaranteed by regional distributors – when it is passed from the high-pressure transmission down to end-users – and what adjustments or considerations might be needed in the distribution network.

Research Questions Addressed

The project posed several key research questions (RQ):

- **RQ1:** *What types of contaminants and at what concentrations are anticipated at various points in a hydrogen distribution network?*
- **RQ2:** *What is the impact of those contaminants on end-user systems and the operation of the distribution network?*
- **RQ3:** *Given findings from RQ1–2, can the indicative EZK-specification (99.5% H₂) be **guaranteed** at the regional distribution level, and what happens if it is not?*
- **RQ4:** *What recommendations or modifications to the EZK-specification are advisable for distribution networks?*

RQ1: *What types of contaminants and at what concentrations are anticipated at various points in a hydrogen distribution network?*

Sources of contaminants: The study identified three broad sources of hydrogen contamination in distribution grids:

1. Carry-over from transmission (the allowable 0.5% contamination left in the EZK-spec).
2. Production-side errors on the distribution level (contaminants from electrolysis, ammonia cracking etc.)
3. Distribution operations incidents (air ingress, mine dust etc.).

To explore realistic worst cases, the project defined **nine contamination scenarios** (six distribution-level incidents and three production-side errors) covering a range of contaminants. These scenarios introduce a variety of contaminants to the network (air through ingress, nitrogen through a faulty purge etc.). These scenarios will be used for the assessment of end-user impact and operational equipment.

RQ2: *What is the impact of those contaminants on end-user systems and the operation of the distribution network?*

Combustion:

- **The effect of the production errors and operational air/water ingress on the flammability limits of hydrogen can be significant.** Bulk contamination (>1%) of inert diluents (N₂, CO₂, etc.) *lower the Wobbe index* of hydrogen, meaning appliances receive less heat input for the same volume of gas. Most of the worst-case scenarios above would push the Wobbe index of the gas below specified minimum of 45.99 MJ/m³.
- This limit is only reached *after* the hydrogen purity level has dropped below 99.5%. 99.3% H₂ contaminated with 0.7% N₂ (or even 1.1% methane) **still adheres to the Wobbe index limit and is therefore relatively acceptable to gas-burning appliances (>98% from HyDelta 3 WP1a).**
- Effects on the composition of the water content of the flue gas and CO₂ and NO_x emissions from expected contaminations were found to be minimal.

- Hydrogen flames burn relatively fast; adding slower burning gases slows the flame. In tests and computational analyses performed by DNV, it is found that contamination can cut the laminar burning velocity by 30–50% under specific circumstances.
- Lean-premixed burners (common in hydrogen boilers for NO_x control) are particularly sensitive; a 5–10% inerts addition was observed to lift or blow off flames in lab studies. However, flame stability is highly dependent on burner design in general.
- Modern fuel/air control systems on burners can compensate for moderate composition shifts.
- It is at this point unclear what appliances would be used by customers attached to distribution networks. **An inventory will have to be made to determine the respective tolerance to changes in Wobbe index and flame stability of each appliance category.**
- Engines and turbines can compensate for changes in Wobbe index, but are affected by rapid changes in Wobbe index when adjusted for hydrogen combustion.

Safety:

- **The effect of the production errors and operational air/water ingress on the flammability limits of hydrogen is found to be insignificant for the contamination levels used.**
- Several of the contamination scenarios have odours which could mask odorants, but the event of a leak and a significant contamination occurring is unlikely. Air/water ingress will not mask odorization.
- Some hydrogen-specific contaminants such as ammonia from ammonia cracking and BTEX-type components from LOHC dehydrogenation can be toxic and require special considerations.
- Besides the abovementioned novel contaminants, the same safety aspects from natural gas infrastructure apply.

Feedstock:

- **Several contaminants can significantly affect catalysts typical for industrial hydrogen end-users.**
- Sulfur and HCl contamination affects methanol and SAF production (Fischer-Tropsch). The Haber-Bosch process is sensitive to oxygen containing molecules (CO₂, CO, O₂). Food production processes are sensitive to sulphur.
- However, it is expected that industrial end-users will have purification systems when they decide to use hydrogen from the national/regional network. Industrial processes currently use hydrogen above 99.5% quality, typically.

Operational end-users:

- **The accuracy of ultrasonic flow meters could be significantly impacted by contamination due to changes in speed of sound of the gas and the lack of accurate models.**
- The accuracy of Coriolis meters is less likely to be affected, at least for measuring the total flow (contaminant + bulk hydrogen). Turbine meters can be affected by particulates at higher flow rates, but this is not a hydrogen-specific effect.
- The inclusion of a particulate limit in the EZK-specification can help operators better design preventive maintenance for filters and rotating machinery.
- Bulk contamination can affect required compressor power in compression systems.
- The release of HCl (hydrogen chloride) due to a pipe fire can rapidly increase the corrosion of metallic parts, but this effect also occurs in natural gas transport/distribution.

- No additional corrosion effects due to interaction with hydrogen are expected from water ingress.
- No specific interactions between hydrogen and mine dust could be identified through analysis of the formation mechanisms.
- Ammonia is not expected to be liquid under normal transport conditions and expected partial pressures.

RQ3: *Given findings from RQ1–2, can the indicative EZK-spec (99.5% H₂) be guaranteed at the regional distribution level, and what happens if it is not?*

Based on the identified scenarios and impacts, it is concluded that it will be challenging to guarantee 99.5% H₂ purity at all points of a regional network under all conditions. In particular, low-pressure distribution pipelines (e.g. <1 bar polymer networks that might supply future residential or small commercial users) are vulnerable to purity loss during normal operation due to possible air and water ingress. If the hydrogen entering the distribution system already contains the maximum allowed 0.5% inert gases, even a minor addition of air or nitrogen internally will push the gas off spec (exceeding the 0.5% contaminant limit). Scenario analysis showed that in a worst-case period of no-flow, purity could drop by a few percentage points in a matter of weeks without any active intervention. This means strict adherence to 99.5% may not be realistic 100% of the time in distribution grids, especially during periods of no flow due to no demand (e.g. summer in a rural network).

The Wobbe index specification (which governs combustion interchangeability) is slightly more forgiving than the purity spec. The EZK specification Wobbe limit would allow roughly up to 0.7% nitrogen dilution before violating heating value requirements. In fact, literature suggests many appliances could tolerate up to ~1% N₂ (or more hydrocarbons) without issues, corresponding to a Wobbe range about 4 MJ/m³ wide. This implies that, when the Wobbe limit is adhered to, hydrogen below 99.5% purity (0.5% contaminants) would likely still meet thermal input and flame stability criteria for a range of residential combustion equipment expected downstream of lower-pressure pipelines (though not fuel cells or very purity-sensitive processes).

RQ4: *What recommendations or modifications to the EZK-specification are advisable for distribution networks?*

- Based on this study and previous work for HyDelta, it could be difficult to adhere to the 99.5% hydrogen quality as both an entry and an exit specification for low-pressure networks due to air and water ingress and scenarios with low flow.
- **The 99.5% purity limit could be relaxed for low-pressure distribution infrastructure (below x bar) when combustion is the end-use.** However, the hydrogen should still adhere to a firmly established Wobbe limit, Wobbe rate of change limit, and a minimum of 98% hydrogen purity.
- Toxic and contaminants dangerous to end-users at low-pressure infrastructure, such as oxygen and sulfur compounds, should still be firmly limited. Light hydrocarbons have the lowest impact on combustion equipment, followed by inert gases (nitrogen), and are the most likely candidates for relaxed contaminant limits.
- After gas has passed down to a pressure of relaxed hydrogen purity, it should not be allowed to be boosted up to the national hydrogen network without purification.
- The 99.5% purity limit can be maintained for higher pressure distribution infrastructure above x bar.

- The cut-off pressure x can be based the end-use equipment expected below a certain pressure, and further research on air/water ingress in hydrogen distribution equipment.

Samenvatting

Belangrijkste punten:

- Als de waterstof uit het transportnetwerk al verontreinigd is, kan het moeilijk zijn om in het hergebruikte gasdistributienet te voldoen aan de 99,5% zuiverheidsnorm die is vastgesteld in de door EZK voorgestelde waterstofsificatie in distributienetten (met name onder <1 bar).
 - Als de zuiverheidsnorm (de >99,5 vol% H₂) wordt versoepeld onder een specifieke distributiedruk (bijvoorbeeld $\geq 200\text{mbar}$ of $\geq 1\text{ bar}$), en in plaats daarvan de Wobbe-indexlimiet wordt gebruikt, kan er meer verontreiniging worden getolereerd. Dit zou waterstof distributie in hergebruikte leidingen vergemakkelijken.
 - De hoeveelheid verontreiniging die door verbrandingsapparatuur geïnstalleerd bij eindgebruikers kan worden getolereerd, wordt bepaald door het type verontreiniging. De Wobbe-index kan worden gebruikt om dit te evalueren.
 - Aangezien eindgebruikers van <4 bar leidingen overwegend verbrandingseindgebruikers zijn, is de Wobbe-index een relevantere limiet dan alleen de zuiverheidspecificatie.
 - De snelheid van verandering in waterstofzuiverheid moet echter wel beperkt blijven. Specifieke gevaarlijke verontreinigingen (ammoniak etc.) moeten altijd worden beperkt, ongeacht het drukniveau.
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Waterstof staat op het punt om op grote schaal te worden geïmplementeerd in de Nederlandse economie. Het vroegtijdig vastleggen van kwaliteitsspecificaties is essentieel om te waarborgen dat het geleverde gas consistent is voor eindgebruikers en om de integriteit van de infrastructuur te beschermen. In aardgasnetwerken zijn strikte kwaliteitseisen wettelijk vastgelegd, zodat klanten weten wat ze kunnen verwachten. Voor waterstof bestaat deze wetgeving nog niet, wat onzekerheid creëert voor producenten, netbeheerders en eindgebruikers.

Een nationale richtlijn voor 99,5% zuiverheid (de EZK-specificatie) is voorgesteld (maar nog niet opgenomen in de *Energiewet* of overgenomen door distributeurs, wel door de landelijke netbeheerder) voor het toekomstige landelijke waterstofnetwerk. Het is echter onduidelijk of deze zuiverheid ook in het distributienetwerk (RNB-net) gehandhaafd kan worden. In tegenstelling tot hogedruksystemen (transportsystemen), hebben distributiesystemen meer aftakkingen (zijn een decentraler systeem) en daardoor gevoeliger voor verontreinigingen tijdens normale bedrijfsvoering. Daarnaast kunnen zich onvoorziene incidenten voordoen.

Dit werkpakket onderzoekt of de 99,5% waterstofzuiverheid (met gereguleerde odorisatie) daadwerkelijk gegarandeerd kan worden door regionale netbeheerders – vanaf de overdracht van het hogedruktransportnet tot aan de eindgebruiker – en welke aanpassingen of overwegingen nodig zijn in het distributienetwerk.

Onderzoeksvragen

Om deze uitdaging aan te pakken, zijn de volgende onderzoeksvragen geformuleerd:

- **RQ1:** Welke soorten verontreinigingen en in welke concentraties worden verwacht op verschillende punten in een waterstof distributienetwerk?

- **RQ2:** Wat is de impact van deze verontreinigingen op eindgebruikerssystemen en de werking van het distributienetwerk?
- **RQ3:** Kunnen, op basis van de bevindingen uit RQ1 en RQ2, de EZK-specificaties (99,5% H₂) worden gegarandeerd op regionaal distributieniveau, en wat zijn de gevolgen als dat niet lukt?
- **RQ4:** Welke aanbevelingen of aanpassingen aan de EZK-specificatie zijn wenselijk voor distributienetwerken?

RQ1: Welke soorten verontreinigingen en in welke concentraties worden verwacht op verschillende punten in een waterstofdistributienetwerk?

De studie identificeerde drie hoofdoorzaken van verontreiniging in distributienetten:

1. **Overdracht vanuit het transportnet** (de toegestane 0,5% verontreiniging volgens de EZK-specificatie).
2. **Fouten aan de productiezijde** (bijv. verontreinigingen door elektrolyse, ammoniakkrakers die invoeden op het distributienet).
3. **Operationele fouten, onregelmatigheden en incidenten in distributie** (bijv. luchtintrede mijnstof).

Om realistische worst-cases te onderzoeken, zijn negen scenario's gedefinieerd (zes operationele incidenten en drie productiegerelateerde fouten), die een breed scala aan verontreinigingen introduceren (zoals luchtinlek, stikstof door foutieve spoeling, enz.). Deze scenario's vormen de basis voor de beoordeling van de impact op eindgebruikers en operationele apparatuur.

RQ2: Wat is de impact van deze verontreinigingen op eindgebruikerssystemen en de werking van het distributienetwerk?

Verbranding:

- Productiefouten en lucht-/waterinlek kunnen de ontvlambaarheidsgrenzen van waterstof beïnvloeden. Bulkverontreiniging (>1%) met inerte gassen (N₂, CO₂, etc.) verlaagt de Wobbe-

index, wat leidt tot minder warmte-inbreng per volume-eenheid gas. Enkele worstcases vastgesteld in dit rapport brengen de Wobbe-index onder de ondergrens van 45,99 MJ/m³.

- Deze grens wordt pas overschreden wanneer de zuiverheid onder 99,5% daalt. 99,3% H₂ met 0,7% N₂ (of zelfs 1,1% methaan) blijft binnen de Wobbe-grens en is dus relatief acceptabel voor gasverbrandingsapparatuur (>98% volgens HyDelta 3 WP1a).
- De invloed op de samenstelling van het rookgas (watergehalte, CO₂, NO_x) is minimaal.
- Waterstofvlammen branden relatief snel; toevoeging van trager brandende gassen vertraagt de vlam. Door DNV uitgevoerd testen tonen aan dat verontreiniging de laminaire brandsnelheid met 30–50% kan verlagen.
- Arm voorgemengde branders (veelgebruikt in waterstofketels voor NO_x-reductie) zijn bijzonder gevoelig; toevoeging van 5–10% inerte gassen kan leiden tot vlamopheffing of -uitval. Vlamstabiliteit is echter sterk afhankelijk van het branderontwerp.
- Moderne branders met gasluchtregeling kunnen kleine samenstellingsveranderingen compenseren.
- Het is momenteel onduidelijk welke apparaten eindgebruikers zullen gebruiken. Een inventarisatie is nodig om de toleranties per apparaat type te bepalen.
- Motoren en turbines kunnen Wobbe-index veranderingen compenseren, maar zijn gevoelig voor snelle fluctuaties bij waterstofverbranding.

Veiligheid:

- De invloed van verontreinigingen op de ontvlambaarheidsgrenzen is bij de onderzochte concentraties verwaarloosbaar.
- Sommige verontreinigingen hebben een geur die odoranten kan maskeren, maar de kans op gelijktijdige lekkage en verontreiniging is klein. Lucht-/waterinlek maskeert odorisatie niet.
- Specifieke verontreinigingen zoals ammoniak (uit krakers) en BTEX (uit LOHC) zijn toxisch en vereisen extra aandacht.
- Buiten deze nieuwe verontreinigingen gelden dezelfde veiligheidsmaatregelen als in aardgasinfrastructuur.

Gebruik van waterstof als grondstof in de industrie:

- Diverse verontreinigingen kunnen katalysatoren in industriële processen ernstig beïnvloeden.
- Zwavel en HCl (waterstofchloride) beïnvloeden methanol- en SAF-productie (Fischer-Tropsch). Het Haber-Bosch-proces is gevoelig voor zuurstofhoudende moleculen (CO₂, CO, O₂). Voedselproductie is gevoelig voor zwavel.
- Industriële eindgebruikers zullen waarschijnlijk zuiveringssystemen installeren bij gebruik van waterstof uit het nationale/regionale net. Momenteel gebruiken zij doorgaans waterstof van >99,5% zuiverheid.

Operationele eindgebruikers:

- De nauwkeurigheid van ultrasone flowmeters kan worden beïnvloed door verontreinigingen (verandering in geluidssnelheid).
- Coriolis-meters zijn minder gevoelig. Turbinemeters kunnen beïnvloed worden door deeltjes bij hoge stroomsnelheden, maar dit is geen specifiek waterstofprobleem.
- Het opnemen van een deeltjeslimiet in de EZK-specificatie kan helpen bij onderhoudsplanung.
- Bulkverontreiniging kan het benodigde compressorvermogen beïnvloeden.
- HCl (bijv. door een pijpbrand) kan corrosie versnellen, maar dit geldt ook voor aardgasinfrastructuur.

- Geen extra corrosie verwacht door interactie tussen waterstof en waterinlek.
- Geen specifieke interacties tussen waterstof en mijnstof geïdentificeerd.
- Ammoniak zal onder normale transportcondities niet condenseren.

RQ3: Kan 99,5% zuiverheid worden gegarandeerd voor distributienetten?

Deze studie concludeert op basis van vorig HyDelta werk dat het moeilijk zal zijn om onder alle omstandigheden 99,5% H₂-zuiverheid te garanderen in het volledige regionale distributienet. Vooral lage druk delen van het netwerk (<1 bar, kunststofleidingen) zijn gevoelig voor lucht-/waterinlek. Als het gas al 0,5% inerte gassen bevat vanuit landelijke transportnet, kan zelfs een kleine extra inlek het gas buiten specificatie brengen in het distributienet. In een worstcasescenario zonder doorstroming in een lagedrukleiding kan de zuiverheid binnen enkele weken met meerdere procenten dalen.

De Wobbe-indexspecificatie is iets toleranter dan de zuiverheidsspecificatie. De EZK-grens laat tot ongeveer 0,7% N₂ toe voordat de ondergrens wordt overschreden. Literatuur suggereert dat veel apparaten tot ~1% N₂ of meer kunnen verdragen, wat overeenkomt met een Wobbe-bandbreedte van ongeveer 4 MJ/m³. Dit betekent dat waterstof onder de 99,5% zuiverheid nog steeds aan de thermische en vlamstabiliteitscriteria kan voldoen voor huishoudelijke apparatuur (maar niet voor brandstofcellen of processen die hoge zuiverheid vereisen).

RQ4: Aanbevelingen voor de EZK-specificatie

- Het kan moeilijk zijn om 99,5% H₂-zuiverheid als zowel invoer- als uitvoerspecificatie te hanteren in lage druknetten vanwege lucht-/waterinlek en stilstand.
- De zuiverheidseis kan worden versoepeld voor lage druk (<x bar), mits voldaan wordt aan een vastgestelde Wobbe-grens, een limiet op de Wobbe-veranderingssnelheid en een minimum van 98% H₂.
- Toxische en gevaarlijke verontreinigingen (zoals zuurstof en zwavelverbindingen) moeten streng beperkt blijven. Licht ontvlambare koolwaterstoffen en inerte gassen (zoals N₂) zijn de meest geschikte kandidaten voor versoepeling.
- Gas dat onder een lagere zuiverheidsspecificatie valt in het distributienet, mag niet zonder zuivering teruggevoerd worden naar het landelijke transportnet.
- De 99,5% zuiverheidsspecificatie blijft van kracht voor hogere drukniveaus (>x bar).
- De grensdruk x kan worden bepaald op basis van het type eindgebruikersapparatuur onder dat drukniveau en verder onderzoek naar lucht-/waterinlek in distributie-infrastructuur

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Terms and definitions

This document includes an extensive discussion on the future hydrogen network in relation to the current regulatory framework for natural gas. Dutch gas laws are in Dutch, and terms are not often clearly translated. This can be confusing. Therefore, specific terms will be explained here and will be used consistently throughout the report [1], [2], [3]:

Natural gas:

Gaswet: Dutch gas laws. This law is to be replaced by the *Energiewet* in ~2026-2027, but this is still work in progress.

M+R station: (nl: *meet- en regelstations*) M+R stations are responsible for pressure reduction between the HTL and RTL, odorization and quantification of the amount of gas delivered.

GOS: (nl: *gasontvangststation*) Pressure reduction and gas delivery station found at any coupling point between Gasunie and an end-user or RNB.

HTL: (nl: *hoofdtransportleidingnet*) National high-pressure network operated by Gasunie between 40-67 bar.

RTL: (nl: *regionaal-transportleidingnet*) Regional intermediate-pressure network operated by Gasunie between 16-40 bar.

National network: (nl: *landelijk gastransportnet*) Is defined in the *Gaswet* as a network which is exclusively or primarily designed to transport gas on a national level. In practice this refers to the HTL and RTL operated by Gasunie Transport Services.

Regional network: (nl: *regionaal gastransportnet*) Is defined in the law as any network *not* operated by the LNB as appointed for a period of ten years under article 2, paragraph 1 of the *Gaswet*. In practice this refers to networks operating up to 8 bar. The coupling between the regional network and the national network, where the pressure is reduced to a maximum of 8 bar in a GOS.

English: DSO, Dutch: RNB: (nl: *Regionale netbeheerder*) Regional operator responsible for the regional network. The RNB of the Netherlands are RENDO, Coteq, Liander, Enexis, Stedin, and Westland Infra.

English TSO, Dutch: LNB: (nl: *landelijke netbeheerder*) National operator responsible for the national network. The sole LNB of the Netherlands is Gasunie Transport Services (GTS).

Connection: (nl: *aansluiting*) Any transition between two networks.

Hydrogen:

EZK-specification: Refers to the “*Indicative quality and temperature specification for Hydrogen Network Netherlands*” [4].

H-HTL: Proposed high pressure hydrogen network operating between 30-50 bar.

H-RDN: Proposed high pressure regional distribution network operating between 1-16 bar.

H-LNB: Designated operator of the national network. In the Netherlands the H-LNB is Hynetwork Services.

H-RNB: Regional network operator responsible for the H-RDN and local networks. These are still undefined, but it is the expectation that a single operator will be responsible for hydrogen distribution.

Pressure reduction station: Station where the pressure is lowered. Other functions such as metering and odorization can take place here.

Booster station: Station where the pressure is increased. Other functions such as deodorization can take place here.

1. Introduction

1.1 Problem context and scope

Hydrogen is on the eve of its large-scale deployment as a pipeline gas. Over the coming decade it is expected that producers, storage operators and end-users will be interconnected through a network of repurposed and newly built transport and distribution pipelines. As with natural gas, defining a quality specification for hydrogen at an early stage is essential. Such a specification limits the contaminants in the transported gas, ensuring that the hydrogen will be of a consistent quality level when it arrives at the end-user and safeguarding pipeline integrity.

The specifications are subsequently encoded into regulations and thus into national law. By doing so, end-users know what natural gas quality to expect upon delivery. However, these regulations do not yet exist for hydrogen, but since repurposing the natural gas network is expected, the existing structure and regulatory framework for natural gas will serve as a starting-off point.

Overall, little is known about what the future hydrogen network will look like. Hynetwork, the future national operator of the hydrogen high pressure network states on their website:

“Hynetwork will only build high-pressure networks. In the future, regional distribution networks can be connected (...). At this moment, the regulatory framework for the coupling of regional networks to the national network is lacking.”

This lack of regulation is a challenge for the future of the hydrogen network, since potential end-users, regional operators and hydrogen producers do not know what to expect. Even when it is assumed that HyNetworks will guarantee the proposed EZK-specification (99.5%) at the grid connection between transport and distribution, it is unclear whether this hydrogen quality can be maintained throughout the distribution network. This uncertainty arises due to several factors:

- Contaminations which can occur during distribution operations (e.g. air ingress during a period of low or no flow).
- Contaminants introduced by hydrogen producers feeding into the distribution network (e.g. oxygen release from an electrolyser).
- Contaminants allowed under the EZK-specification and thus present in the hydrogen stream coming from the transmission network

The objective of this work package is threefold. First, it aims to outline assumptions about what the future network will look like and how it differs from the current natural gas network. Second, the impact of contamination on end-users of the network will be assessed to ascertain the ability of the distribution network to guarantee hydrogen quality. Given the distinct legal requirements at the distribution level, odorization practices will also have to be considered also.

Finally, the ambition of this HyDelta work package is to provide insight into the technical and economic considerations regarding the ability to guarantee hydrogen quality in the distribution part of the network (RNB). This means that both regional and local distribution networks are considered.

1.2 Assumptions about the future (hydrogen) network

To address the objectives of this work package, assumptions will have to be made about the future hydrogen network. Since many properties of the future network are still unknown, the following assumptions/observations are made to anchor the scope of this study:

1. The national high-pressure hydrogen transmission network (H-HTL) will be operated by Hynetwork, a subsidiary of Gasunie, and is expected to operate at pressures between 30-50 bar.
2. The regional hydrogen distribution network (H-RDN) will be operated by multiple regional operators such as Enexis, Stedin and Liander, and is expected to operate at pressure levels between 1-16 bar, as indicated in the HyRegions 2 report [5].
3. If a local industry requires hydrogen at a pressure of 20 bar, the gas will either be compressed from the H-RDN or pressure-reduced from the H-HTL [5] as indicated in the HyRegions 2 report.
4. The Hydrogen Network Netherlands will adopt the *Indicative Quality and Temperature Specification* as recommended by The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy [4], and at least guarantee the hydrogen to this quality at the H-RDN/H-HTL interface.
5. Unique to the new hydrogen system (compared to the existing natural gas system, see Appendix) is the requirement for reverse feed-in from the regional distribution network to the transmission network. This requirement rises from the expectation that hydrogen production will be more decentralized, with a greater share occurring at the regional system level rather than at the transmission system. As a result, the storage capacity of the regional network may reach its capacity limits during periods of high local production, such as in the case of peak production from renewables. To prevent over pressurizing the regional network, excess hydrogen can be compressed and fed into the transmission network, which offers significantly greater capacity. 'Gas boosters' at gas receiving stations (GOS) will be used to compress this feed-in gas to the H-HTL. As a whole, the transfer between higher and lower pressure systems is expected to be more dynamic in the hydrogen infrastructure than in the current natural gas system.
6. Odorants are legally required for distribution by regional network operators (RNB).
7. Sulphur-based odorants can negatively impact industrial processes [3]. For example, the impact of a low concentration of sulphur (2 ppm) can be catastrophic on a fuel cell, reducing output power by 50% [4].
8. Hynetwork specifically states that their focus will be on 'connecting parties operating on high-pressure'¹ (30 bar exit), leading to the assumption that the regional network will **not** operate between 16-30 bar. Hynetwork is only considered responsible for the high-pressure

¹ Page 12, "Conceptvoorstel aanpassing uitrolplan Consultatiedocument 2024" Hynetwork Services, 10-12-2024.

network (>30 bar). The distribution system operated <16 bar will be operated by the RNB.

9. The hydrogen distribution network for pressure at or above 16 bar will make use of steel pipelines. Below 8 bar, polymer pipelines are used.
10. At least in the first iteration of the hydrogen network development, low-pressure residential distribution networks (<1 bar) are not expected. The majority of the end-users will be industrial and commercial and local networks requiring hydrogen at high pressure (>16 bar) and intermediate pressure (1-16 bar).

Figure 1.1: Overview of the known parts of the proposed hydrogen infrastructure in the Netherlands.

Using the above assumptions, this document will address the research questions outlined in the next section. In the Figure above, the expected network structure is presented. Two major systems are subdivided based on pressure levels and the type of infeed and offtake they have. While many aspects of the future hydrogen system remain uncertain, the purpose of this document is to help define local specifications and odorization practices for the evolving network.

1.3 Research Questions

The primary research question of the project is:

“Can the 99.5% hydrogen purity specification (and regulated odorization) be guaranteed at all levels, from high-pressure network to end-users?”

Based on the assumptions, observations and context in the previous chapter, the following research questions (RQ) are posed:

RQ: Realistic hydrogen specifications in distribution grids

- **RQ 1:** What types and concentrations of contaminants are anticipated at various locations within the hydrogen distribution network?
- **RQ 2:** What is the impact of the (in RQ 1) identified contamination levels in distributions grids defined on end-user systems and the overall operation of the distribution network?
- **RQ 3:** Based on the findings from RQ 1 and RQ 2, can the EZK-specification be guaranteed at the regional distribution level (RDN), and what are the potential impacts on end-users? Does the EZK-specification need to be adhered to for the distribution grids?
- **RQ 4:** What recommendations can be made to the EZK-specification for distribution networks?
- **RQ 5:** What are the relevant remaining knowledge gaps and and what future (experimental) research is recommended to address them?

2. Contaminations in hydrogen grids

2.1 What contaminations and at what level are expected at what locations in the distribution network?

As discussed in the introduction, the sources of contaminations are possible in the distribution network:

- The first are allowable concentrations from the high-pressure network as specified in the EZK-specification. These can be consistent and long-lasting, depending on available production in the HTL.
- The second are contamination introduced in the distribution network by connected producers, in error. These are assumed to be temporary.
- The third are contaminants introduced during distribution, by mistake.

2.2 The indicative EZK Specification

First, possible contaminants in the distribution network will have to be identified. Since it is assumed HyNetwork will guarantee the EZK-specification (*“Indicative quality and temperature specification for Hydrogen Network Netherlands”* [4]), all ‘allowable’ contaminants can be expected in the distribution network.

This indicative specification requires a minimum hydrogen purity of 99.5% and sets limits on various contaminants. A full overview is presented in Table 2.1. In this report, this specification is referred to in the text as the *EZK-specification* as a reference to the Dutch ministry who commissioned the 2023 study *“A follow-up study into the hydrogen quality requirements”* [6] and to avoid assigning the specification to any specific network operator.

Table 2.1. EZK specification for the Dutch hydrogen network. It is still legally unclear whether these are entry or exit specs.

Specification	Limit
Wobbe Index	45.99 - 48.35 MJ/(n)m ³ [25/0 °C] ²
Hydrogen Purity	≥ 99.5 mol%
Sum of inert gases (N ₂ , He, Ar)	≤ 0.5 mol-%
Hydrocarbons incl. Methane	≤ 0.5 mol/mol%
Oxygen (O ₂)	≤ 10 μmol/mol (ppm)
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	≤ 20 μmol/mol (ppm)
Carbon monoxide (CO)	≤ 20 μmol/mol (ppm)
Total S content (incl. H ₂ S)	≤ 3 μmol/mol (ppm)
Formic Acid	≤ 10 μmol/mol (ppm)
Formaldehyde (HCHO)	≤ 10 μmol/mol (ppm)
Ammonia (NH ₃)	≤ 10 μmol/mol (ppm)
Halogenated compounds	≤ 0.05 μmol/mol (ppm)
All other impurities	Shall not contain solid, liquid or gaseous material that might interfere with the integrity or operation of pipes or any gas appliance
Water dew point	≤ -8 °C at 70 bar(a)

² The volume in m³ (n) is defined at 0°C (measurement conditions) and 1013.25 mbar. The energy in MJ is derived from the thermodynamic values between 25°C (combustion conditions) at 1013.25 mbar according to ISO 6979. This is the standard Dutch methodology as opposed to [15/15 °C], which is another common standard.

Hydrocarbon dew point	≤ -2°C at 1 - 70 bar(a)
Gas temperature (entry, exit)	5-30°C
Odorants	Undefined

As can be seen in Table 2.1 above, the specification sets limits to contaminants and established a minimum purity level of 99.5%. The specification also includes a derived property of a gas called the Wobbe index, this will be discussed in-depth in the report. In general, the following considerations are made when drafting a specification [4], [7]:

- At a minimum, the specification must ensure the safety, integrity and environmental requirements of both pipeline systems and end-user systems. For example, corrosive gases and liquids are strictly limited.
- The specification and the contaminant limits must be technically achievable.
- Some contaminants, even though they are not corrosive, are restricted as a compromise between producers, end-users, storage operators and other stakeholders.
- Derived properties such as the Wobbe index are defined as a range between a lower and upper limit. As the name implies, derived properties are dependent on the composition of the gas components in the specification, and therefore variable.
- Overly strict specification (e.g. requiring 99.99% hydrogen purity) can limit the number of hydrogen producers able to feed into the network and may discourage cross-border trade activities.

For end-users and network operators, a balance between all the above-listed considerations is essential. This report will assess whether this balance can be maintained after hydrogen has been delivered to the distribution network.

2.3 Possible contaminations in the RDN: Distribution errors

In this paragraph the two different kinds of scenarios will be discussed; ones that are based on operational errors in distribution and ones that are based on hydrogen productions error. These errors lead to the accidental introduction of impurities that may affect the performance of end-use equipment. The scenarios were constructed together with the HyDelta partners from the Expert Assessment Group (EAG) of this work package. Although the scenarios are based on real situations distributors might face, the scenarios are edge cases where the level of contamination has been inflated to clearly illustrate the effects on end-users, and they do not precisely reflect actual contamination levels.

2.3.1 Scenario 1: Odorization error

A new odorization system has been placed at the entry of the distribution network. Due to some mechanical/control failure too much odorant was released into the system for a short while. The resulting odorant levels is 300-600 mg/m³(n), ~100-150 ppm THT, which is a sulfur-based odorant.

2.3.2 Scenario 2: Nitrogen purge error

A pipe section has been isolated for maintenance. The procedure for nitrogen purging of a pipeline after maintenance has not been followed correctly. A significant amount of nitrogen remains in a section of pipeline, which has combined with the re-injected hydrogen. The resulting contaminants are: N₂: 2-5 mol%.

2.3.3 Scenario 3: Short-circuit in power cable near PVC pipe

A short-circuit of an electrical component near a PVC pipeline has occurred and a fire has started. The polymer is degraded because of the heat and acid compounds, and soot are released into the hydrogen gas locally. The resulting contaminants are hydrochloric acid HCl: 100-300 ppm and soot particles.

2.3.4 Scenario 4: Mine dust release

Near Limburg (historical mining region) in the Netherlands, coke oven gas has been transported in both HTL and RTL networks. This has led to fouling of the network with mine dust (cyanide). Immediately after repurposing an older pipe and pigging, a large amount of dust has been released. The resulting contaminants are an elevation of the number of particles (black powder/ mine dust), iron (sulfides), cyanides, sand, mercury. Particle size of the solid particles is 1-15 μm .

2.3.5 Scenario 5: Permeation of atmospheric air or water into the pipeline with low flow

Scenario 8 describes the problem of in-leak of air and water into low-pressure rural pipelines with little to no hydrogen flow ('ingress'). In practice this can occur in a variety of scenarios, such as in a residential area in summertime where hydrogen demand is near-zero, or when an industrial plant is temporarily shut down for any reason. Furthermore, polymeric materials used at low pressure (PVC, HDPE) are generally more sensitive than metals [8], as depicted in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Relative permeability of pipeline materials [8].

This scenario has already been extensively discussed in HyDelta 3.0 WP5D.1 [9]. This work package will use the data presented in HyDelta 3.0 WP1a, in Table 3.1 of Section 3.4. This data has been extrapolated for 100 days of 'no flow' (a situation where, for whatever reason, the flow in the hydrogen pipe has stopped, locally) for the urban and rural low-pressure scenarios in Figure 2.2. These 100 days are modelled for permeation rates in summer, when the rates are higher due to elevated temperatures. 100 days of summer was assessed as being a worst-case scenario due to the typical length of summer (June-August).

Figure 2.2: The reduction of hydrogen purity through in-leak of air and water in rural and urban low-pressure pipelines. Rural pipelines are made of polyethylene polymer.

The Figure above shows the effect of in-leak on polymer pipelines. The same conclusions as drawn in HyDelta 3.0 can be drawn here; in a worst-case scenario the hydrogen in a rural pipeline can fall below the EZK specification of 99.5% in 21 days and would fall to 97.6% in 100 days. This is calculated for pure hydrogen. If it is assumed that the rates of permeation remain the same for contaminated hydrogen (with 0.5% nitrogen, which is still within the EZK specification), any amount of in-leak would immediately bring the gas off-specification, and within 100 days, the hydrogen purity would have dropped down to almost 97%. As can be seen, and as has been identified in HyDelta 3.0, is that higher pressure systems and urban systems are not considered as vulnerable as rural low-pressure systems. Therefore Scenario 8 will consider the rural data only as a worst-case scenario.

2.3.6 Scenario 6: Desorption of odorants from the pipe wall into the hydrogen

When pipes that have historically transported odorized natural gas are repurposed, some of the sulphur-based odorants have been adsorbed into the pipe walls. These can then be released when the pipes are later repurposed for hydrogen. The concentration of desorbed odorant in the gas is dependent on the flow rate, the lower the flow, the higher the concentration of the odorant in the gas.

This scenario has been extensively discussed in previous HyDelta works including HyDelta 1.0 [10] and HyDelta 3.0 [11]. HyDelta 1.0 showed that repeated flushings of pipelines reduces the amount of THT uptake in hydrogen through desorption. PVC and steel pipes had far lower rates of desorption than PE, stating that:

“Desorption does (practically) not occur in steel pipelines”

This rules out desorption in > 8 bar pipelines and lower pressure steel pipelines.

HyDelta 3 WP1a stated that:

The second scenario is that no, or a different, odorant is used. In this case THT is desorbed into the THT-free hydrogen. Figure 3.6 gives an indication of the rate at which this occurs. The maximum value

found is 36 mg/m³. Using the ideal gas law, it can be calculated that this corresponds to 10 ppm (see also Appendix B). Again, percentage wise this has no significant influence on the overall gas quality.

Concluding that there is no significant impact on the overall gas quality (the 99.5% hydrogen purity or the Wobbe index is never at risk). However, it could exceed the sulphur limit initially in a worst-case scenario. Therefore, proper cleaning and flushing of pipelines is required as described in the other HyDelta work packages, since the desorption rate is expected to lower after flushing and frequent use. If the low-pressure part of the distribution grid is odorized with THT, care should be taken to evaluate the combination of the injection of odorant and desorption of odorant in the network.

2.4 Possible contaminations in the RDN: Production errors

As discussed above, three scenarios were defined where contaminants are introduced due to errors occurring during hydrogen production. These will be outlined in detail below. Note that many of these substances are monitored for by net operators and would therefore be prevented from being moved too far through the network by shutting down sections of the grid.

2.4.1 Scenario 7: LOHC dehydrogenation error

One possible import method considered for the Dutch hydrogen network are liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHC). Chemicals such as benzene and xylene can serve as hydrogen carriers. Through hydrogenation, hydrogen is chemically bound to these compounds, enabling easier transport. At the import terminal, the hydrogen can then be released via a dehydrogenation reaction. An error has occurred whilst dehydrogenating imported LOHC at an import terminal. This results in a release of BTEX-contaminated hydrogen into the network. This results in a contamination of [12]: Benzene: 2000 3000-6000 ppm, xylene: 2000-4000 ppm.

2.4.2 Scenario 8: Electrolyser error

Electrolysers produce oxygen and hydrogen from water using electricity. Normally, these gases are separated during the production process. An error has occurred at an electrolyser facility, resulting in a failure of the oxygen/hydrogen separation process. This results in a release of oxygen into the hydrogen network. This results in a contamination of: O₂: 2-5 mol%.

2.4.3 Scenario 9: Ammonia cracker error

Another hydrogen carrier being considered in the Netherlands is ammonia, which is produced from hydrogen and nitrogen. To release the hydrogen the ammonia is 'cracked' using a catalyst and high temperatures. An error has occurred during ammonia cracking. This results in a release of ammonia into the hydrogen network. This results in a contamination of: NH₃: 2-5 mol%. Note that at this time it is not possible to crack ammonia in regional networks, but this could change in the future.

2.5 Summary

The scenarios and the contamination levels have been summarized in Table 2.2. The connection between the scenarios, the network and the research questions is shown in Figure 2.3 below.

Table 2.2: Off-spec contaminant scenarios.

Name	Type	Contaminants
1 Odorization error	Operational	Tetrahydrothiophene (THT): 300-600 mg/m ³ (n), ~100-150 ppm
2 Nitrogen purge error	Operational	N ₂ : 2-5 mol%
3 Short-circuit near polymer (PVC) pipeline	Operational	Hydrochloric acid HCl: 100-300 ppm Soot particles

4 Mine dust release	Operational	Iron (sulfides), cyanides, sand, mercury. Solid particle size is 1-15 μm
5 Air/water in-leak in polymer pipelines	Operational	Depending on the duration of no-flow. For example, the concentration on day 14 is: 812 ppm O ₂ , 2143 + (5000 ppm) N ₂ (~0.71 mol%), 367 ppm H ₂ O
6 Desorption	Operational	Concentration on day 100 is 468 mg/m ³ THT, ~130 ppm
7 LOHC dehydrogenation failure	Production	Benzene: 3000-6000 ppm, Xylene: 2000-4000 ppm
8 Electrolyser error	Production	O ₂ : 2-5 mol%
9 Ammonia cracker error	Production	NH ₃ : 2-5 mol% ³

Figure 2.3: Overview of the potential contaminants sources in the distribution network; the contamination from distribution operation, top-down contamination from the HTL and contamination caused by production errors.

3. What is the impact of the off-spec contaminants on end-users?

To answer this question, the term *impacts* will have to be categorized on what is affected. First, the two most common end uses of hydrogen today are discussed [13]: combustion (burning the hydrogen for heat or work) and feedstock (chemically transforming the hydrogen to other molecules). Besides these, there is also the operational impact (on hydrogen infrastructure; pipelines, compressors, filters, flow meters etc.) and the effect on safety in terms of flammability limits and potential toxicity of the contaminants to operational personnel/end-users.

3.1 Combustion equipment

End-use combustion equipment is designed, optimized, operated and maintained for a specific range of gases across a distribution area. It is well-known that a change in gas composition affects the

³ See 'Note on ammonia' at the end of this chapter.

performance of end-use equipment in terms of (1) thermal input (2) operational changes (air-to-fuel ratio), (3) combustion products (flue gases) and temperatures [14].

3.1.1 Effect on thermal input

3.1.1.1 Impact of contamination scenarios on the Wobbe Index

The thermal input of a process is directly related to the Wobbe Index of the fuel. The Wobbe index is defined as the higher heating value of the fuel (H_s) divided by the square root of the relative density of the fuel.

$$W = \frac{H_s}{\sqrt{\frac{\rho_{fuel}}{\rho_{air}}}}$$

As can be seen in the equation, an increase in the higher heating value H_s will increase the Wobbe Index, conversely, an increase in the relative density of the gas results in a decrease in the Wobbe Index.

Therefore, at low concentrations, the Wobbe Index can be significantly reduced by either very heavy inert gases (such as CO₂) or gases with a high heating value (such as propane). The proposed EZK specification contains a lower Wobbe index (45.99 MJ/m³). Gas having a lower Wobbe index than 45.99 MJ/m³ is not legally allowed in the net. The specification also sets a higher bound which represents pure hydrogen (Wobbe Index of 48.36 MJ/m³).

Figure 3.1 below shows the effect of the scenarios on the Wobbe index. The contaminants discussed in the scenarios always result in a lower Wobbe index. Therefore, the upper bound will never be exceeded. Furthermore, as can be seen in the Figure, except for scenario 7 (the LOHC scenario), the scenarios shown result in a Wobbe index below the legal limit. For LOHC, the 3000/2000 ppm scenario is still above the legal limit, while the other scenario is outside the limit. Although not shown, scenario 1 and 3 resulted in Wobbe index values within the allowed Wobbe bandwidth.

Figure 3.1: Changes in Wobbe Index due to the contaminants from the scenarios. Low and high contaminant levels are chosen and are represented by the light and dark blue bars respectively. The dotted double bar is the upper Wobbe Index limit of pure hydrogen, and the double solid bar is the minimum Wobbe limit from the indicative EZK specification.

As can be seen in Figure 3.1 above, the Wobbe Index can be impacted significantly by trace components. Since these composition changes are due to production/operation errors, it is assumed that the composition will change suddenly for a brief period of time.

Scenario 5, the ingress of air and water into a rural pipeline, has been analysed as a function of time. The impact of permeation is a long-term effect, however, and has been calculated in Figure 3.2 below.

Figure 3.2: The reduction of Wobbe index through in-leak of air and water in rural pipelines for pure hydrogen and pre-contaminated hydrogen.

As seen in the Figure, the Wobbe index specification leaves more room for contamination than the purity specification as depicted in Figure 2.2. Using the same permeation rates pure hydrogen would fall below the Wobbe specification of 45.99 in ~30 days, and contaminated hydrogen (5% H₂) would fall below the Wobbe specification in ~8 days. Therefore, there is **more room in hydrogen purity level when taking only the Wobbe as a limiting factor**. In other words; a relaxation of the purity specification for rural networks would allow for some no-flow in summer to be tolerable without exceeding the Wobbe specification.

Therefore, it can be stated that when only the Wobbe index is limited in the specification, but the purity is not, there is more tolerance for permeation in low-pressure distribution networks.

As mentioned above, hydrogen on the edge of the hydrogen specification at 99.5% H₂/0.5% N₂ would remain above the Wobbe spec for 7.5 days. However, if the hydrogen arrives from the H-HTL with other allowed contaminants, such as 0.5% hydrocarbons, the time before falling below the Wobbe Index specification would be longer, as can be seen in Figure 3.3, where the effect of air ingress on contaminated hydrogen is shown.

Figure 3.3: Impact of type of contaminants on the allotted time before hydrogen in a rural pipeline with no flow falls below the EZK Wobbe specification. Air ingress under different initial hydrogen contaminations (99.5% H₂ + 0.5% methane, ethane, propane or nitrogen). The days when the Wobbe lower limit is exceeded, and the hydrogen percentage at that point is noted in the Figure.

Figure 3.3 shows how contamination with methane and, although unlikely to be present in the network, higher hydrocarbons allow more room for air ingress within the Wobbe limit. This can be explained by the high heating value of these gases, whereas nitrogen is inert. This implies that the sensitivity of end-user equipment to contamination through permeation also depends on the **pre-existing contamination** present in the hydrogen passed down from the H-HTL.

3.1.1.2 Impact on end-user equipment

Now the impact of contaminant scenarios on the Wobbe index has been established, the tolerance of combustion appliances to changes in the Wobbe index should be investigated. Unfortunately, the impact of Wobbe variation of most residential and industrial appliances is a knowledge gap. This is partly due to the lack of development in pure-hydrogen appliances and since it is unknown what specific appliances will be used by end-users connected to the future hydrogen distribution network. What is known will be outlined below, but more experimental research is needed to fully evaluate whether the current Wobbe bandwidth established in the EZK specification is sufficiently stringent for all future appliances.

Turbines for power generations are highly tuned to a specific composition or range to reduce emissions and increase efficiency [15]. Therefore, power generation plants require a slow rate of change in the composition of the gas, defined by a limit to the change in Wobbe (ΔW). A sudden onset of a bulk contamination such as nitrogen or oxygen at high percentages can negatively affect these power generation systems, especially if the contamination has a long duration. Some evidence suggests, that when the rate of change is low enough, natural gas turbines have a Wobbe tolerance around 5% fluctuation [16]. A suggested limit to the rate of change established in collaboration with stakeholders is $\Delta W < 0.5\text{-}1 \text{ MJ/m}^3\cdot\text{minute}$ [17] for hydrogen turbines and engines.

Industrial gas engines, such as those used in CHP applications (combined heat and power, Dutch: *warmte-krachtkoppeling WKK*) are dependent on two fuel properties; methane number (knock resistance of a fuel) [18] and heating value (Wobbe Index without the density component; fuel injection systems are mass-based). The characteristics of a CHP engine running on hydrogen are very dependent on the engine, and therefore no clear limits to changes in these fuel properties can be established. Reference [19] offers some guidance on hydrogen purity in internal combustion engines. This document describes two hydrogen qualities with 98%, where grade F-2 is specified for stationary (CHP) applications. This specification only specifies a maximum of 2% non-hydrogen gases, with a 0.5% limit on gases without heating value. The rationale for these limits is [17]:

“With an increasing contamination level of hydrogen gas, the energy intake into an engine is disproportionately reduced. [...] By limiting the sum of the main impurities oxygen (O₂), nitrogen (N₂), argon (Ar) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) to a maximum of 5 000 μmol/mol, the specified hydrogen grades F-1 and F-2 provide at least 93 % of the inferior Wobbe Index of pure hydrogen. [...] In instances where a larger reduction of the inferior Wobbe Index is present, some adaptation of the engine can be needed.”

This rationale and the maximum level of inert gases aligns with the proposed EZK hydrogen specification.

Burners for industrial heat (such as brick firing) can be categorized in two categories: indirect heat burners and direct heat burners. Direct burners rely on a certain flue gas composition which directly influences the end-product, this will be discussed in later sections on changes in emissions. Indirect burners are used for heating another medium such as water or air. Both are affected by changes in Wobbe Index. DBI-GUT states in a 2022 analysis that a Wobbe fluctuation of 2% is acceptable for industrial hydrogen burners, which suggests a Wobbe band of about 2 MJ/m³ establishing a lower bound at 46.36 MJ/m³ which is more stringent than the EZK-specification [16]. However, the reasoning behind this 2% fluctuation tolerance was not fully included in the report.

For residential boilers/furnaces and other appliances, the Wobbe tolerance is unknown. In the following chapter, it will be discussed how residential hydrogen-burning appliances are expected to burn relatively fuel-lean due to the high burning velocity of hydrogen. This differs from natural gas appliances, and the Wobbe Index tolerance in this combustion regime with hydrogen to contaminants has not been explored. Here, experimental work is recommended to further refine the minimum Wobbe specification for hydrogen-burning residential appliances. The beforementioned DBI report suggests a lower Wobbe limit of ~44 MJ/m³ (translated from 42 [15/15 °C]) for residential appliances [16] allowing up to 2% inert components. This is significantly more relaxed than the EZK-specification. The supporting rationale for this number in that specific report is based on the UK Hy4Heat project [20]. The Wobbe band in that report has been based on natural gas appliances (UK standard GSMR1996), and the report has been reviewed and approved by gas appliance manufacturers. This suggests that the practical Wobbe variation tolerance of hydrogen appliances could be larger than those specified in the current iteration of the EZK specification, but more supporting experimental evidence is needed.

3.1.1.3 Conclusions

Based on the above analysis, the following conclusions can be made:

- Scenarios 2, 7, 8, 9 and 5 (permeation) can all put the Wobbe index below the EZK specification.

- There is more room in hydrogen purity level when taking only the Wobbe as a limiting factor. This means that even though a contaminated hydrogen composition does not adhere to the purity requirement, the Wobbe requirement is still met.
- The above-mentioned room in the Wobbe index could allow some tolerance for no-flow situations in distribution networks during the summer period when permeation rates are high.
- Although the EZK specification sets a lower limit for Wobbe requirements, there is a lack of experimental work supporting this limit. Experimental work could characterize the lower Wobbe bound for future hydrogen appliance types. Evidence from this work can support arguments why purity levels below 99.5% could be tolerated in distribution networks or not. Literature suggests that the Wobbe tolerance of residential appliances could be wider than the proposed Wobbe lower limit in the EZK-specification.
- It is at this point unclear what appliances would be used by customers attached to distribution networks. An inventory will have to be made to determine the respective tolerance to changes in Wobbe index of each appliance category.
- Power turbines typically require limitation to the rate of change in Wobbe index of a fuel. This has not yet been specified in the EZK proposed specification.
- The EZK-specification is aligned with ISO's recommendation for internal combustion engines.

3.1.2 Flame stability

3.1.2.1 *The equivalence ratio*

A fuel such as hydrogen has the following requirement of oxygen for complete combustion:

Here, it can be seen that hydrogen only requires half a mole of oxygen per molecule of fuel. Combustion is considered rich when there is more hydrogen than required for complete combustion, and lean when there is insufficient hydrogen to fully combust. To indicate whether there is rich or lean combustion, the equivalence ratio is often used. This equivalence ratio (ϕ) represents the fuel-to-air ratio. For complete combustion the ϕ is 1, while for rich combustion the $\phi > 1$ and for lean combustion the $\phi < 1$.

Returning to the problem of contaminants in fuel, this means that any change in the fuel, such as contamination, leads to dilution of the fuel, and hence lowering the ϕ .

Figure 3.4: Example of an attached flame (left) and a lifted flame by admixing CO_2 (right).

In a burner system, two factors are important for flame stability: the outflow velocity of the fuel and air and the burning velocity. These are depicted in the above Figure. Without active control, an appliance is not aware of the incoming gas composition. This means the outflow will remain the same. However, changes in gas composition changes the burning velocity. In increase in burning velocity will result in a flame moving towards the burner surface (flashback). While decreasing the burning velocity results in the flame moving away from the burner surface. When the burning velocity decreases too much, the flame lifts off from the burner and extinguishes. In the worst-case flame extinction can lead to a release of fuel into the oven/environment [21], which is a safety issue.

Appliances are adjusted to a specific equivalence ratio. Figure 3.5 shows the relationship between burning velocity and equivalence ratio.

Figure 3.5: Laminar burning velocities of hydrogen at various equivalence ratios. Compilation of public data. From [22].

As can be seen in the figure, appliances calibrated around the stoichiometric line (dotted line in the figure) will see a significant decrease in burning velocity when the fuel becomes leaner (moving from the dotted line to the left) and a more moderate increase when the fuel becomes richer. Appliances calibrated at low equivalence ratios ($0.5 < \phi < 0.75$) are placed in a very 'steep' region for burning velocity and any shift to the left (leaner) will significantly impact the burning velocity.

3.1.2.3 Impact of contamination scenarios on the burning velocity

Now, the impact of contamination on the burning velocity can be discussed. The impact will be calculated at various equivalent ratios to represent multiple combustion modes. In hydrogen end-use, many appliances are expected to operate under lean combustion. In this case we assume an equivalence ratios of 0.6 and 0.75. To calculate the burning velocity in diffusion burners in the industry, stoichiometric ($\phi=1$) combustion is included as well. The burning velocity of the fuel/air mixtures were calculated in using the PREMIX code [23] from the CHEMKIN II suite [24], using the USC Mech Version II reaction mechanism [25].

For illustrative purposes, Figure 3.6 shows the impact of Scenario 5 (the permeation of nitrogen, oxygen and water in the pipeline at low pressure). The data has been normalized to show the relative reduction in burning velocity. As can be seen in the Figure, 100 days of summer days without flow can lead to a reduction in burning velocity of 53% for lean ($\phi = 0.6$) burners. Burners operating at stoichiometric conditions are affected less, and only experience a reduction of 23%, compared to the combustion of pure hydrogen.

Figure 3.6: Normalized (the burning velocity of hydrogen with contaminants compared to pure hydrogen) burning velocity for lean and stoichiometric combustion with increasing amounts of contaminants due to permeation. After 100 summer days without flow, the hydrogen has been reduced to ~97%.

This phenomenon where lean combustion experiences a larger reduction in burning velocity due to contamination can be explained by the steep slope Figure 3.5. Any appliance left of the stoichiometric line is increasingly vulnerable to dilution (becoming leaner) resulting in a lowered burning velocity when contaminants are present in the fuel. Therefore, appliances adjusted to burn leaner are more vulnerable.

Table 3.1: Numerically calculated burning velocities and changes in equivalence ratio for a lean and stoichiometric ($\phi = 0.75$, $\phi = 1$) combustion process. The flame velocities for 5% nitrogen and 5% oxygen contamination at $\phi = 0.5$ fell outside the normal parameters of the model.

Combustion mode	Property	H ₂	H ₂ + 2% N ₂ (Scenario 2)	H ₂ + 5% N ₂ (Scenario 2)	H ₂ + 2% O ₂ (Scenario 8)	H ₂ + 5% O ₂ (Scenario 8)
$\phi = 0.6$	S _L [cm/s]	108.7	67.6	n/a*	53.3	n/a*
	%Reduction in S _L	0	-37%	n/a	-51%	n/a
$\phi = 0.75$	S _L [cm/s]	180	120	84	120	47
	%Reduction in S _L	0	-33%	-53%	-33%	-74%
$\phi = 1$	S _L [cm/s]	258	218	168	204	126
	%Reduction in S _L	0	-16%	-35%	-21%	-51%

This trend continues for the contaminant scenarios. As can be seen in Table 3.1, the contaminant scenarios can have a significant impact on burning velocity. Again, lean-burning appliances are more

vulnerable to blow-off than stoichiometric appliances and the reduction in burning velocity is significantly greater. For very lean combustion at $\phi = 0.6$, the equivalence ratio shifted to values which fell outside the allowable parameters of the reaction model and were therefore not included. Although not simulated here⁴, ammonia and BTEX are expected to make the combustion leaner, but to a less of a degree than for the contaminants in the other scenarios.

3.1.2.4 Impact on end-user equipment

As seen in the previous section, contamination can have a significant reducing effect on burning velocity. This reduction can make the flame ‘settle’ further from the burner, as the burning velocity reduces relative to the exit velocity of the fuel. In the worst case, blow-off can occur where the flame extinguishes. In the latter event, hydrogen can be released into the room where the burner is placed, which is a significant risk [26], as has also been thoroughly evaluated in other HyDelta work packages. Therefore, it is important to characterize at what level of reduction in burning velocity:

- Flame instability occurs and what the consequences are.
- Blow-off occurs.

Recent work [27] characterized the extinction behaviour for nitrogen-diluted hydrogen flames, finding that a nitrogen fraction of 5-10% can lead to lifting depending on the fuel velocity, and higher percentages (15-20%) can lead to flame extinction. It was also found that burner nozzle thickness was a significant influence, supporting the argument that flame stability is very design dependent. Similar work also supports the 15-20% nitrogen dilution blowoff [28] percentage at various equivalence ratios and the effect of burner design. Therefore, it is possible that large (>5%) leaks of N_2 , O_2 , or any other gases without heating value (Ar, CO_2 , CO) could lead to some flame instability [26]. However, a general limit cannot be set on the basis of this scientific research in lab conditions. Experimental work with real residential and industrial is required, and the flame stability has to be assessed for each burner type.

It should be noted that the calculated reduction in burning velocity in the previous section assumed that there was no *fuel/air control* present in the systems, and that the amount of air for combustion was pre-determined as a calibration setting in the appliance. Fuel/air control systems are designed to adjust the amount of supplied fuel and air when required. This can be achieved by feedback (by, for example, detecting the amount of air in the flue gas) or feedforward (based on the known composition of the fuel) control systems. These systems keep the equivalence ratio steady. This greatly reduces the impact of contaminants on the burning velocity as shown below in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Illustration of the effect of fuel/air control (maintaining a steady ratio of air and fuel, and thus equivalence ratio) on the impact of contaminants on burning velocity.

$\phi = 0.6$	H_2	$H_2 + 2\% N_2$ Without fuel/air control	$H_2 + 2\% N_2$ With fuel/air control	$H_2 + 5\% N_2$ With fuel/air control
S_L [cm/s]	108.7	67.6	107.1	104.52
Shifted	0.6	0.52	0.6	0.6
% SL reduction	0	-37%	-1.5%	-3.8%

⁴ The burning velocities for hydrogen/ammonia and hydrogen/BTEX mixtures have not yet been adequately described at these lean conditions to make an accurate comparison.

From the above analysis it can be concluded that fuel/air control can be a significant mitigator of reductions in burning velocity due to contamination. However, for such a system to work the response by the controller should be fast enough. For example, a feedback system with a response time of 20 seconds could leave enough time for a flame to extinguish during a major contamination of the hydrogen network. Feedforward systems should be more rapid, based on the sample rate.

Finally, the permeation scenario includes water ingress. The maximum calculated water ingress after 100 days of no flow in a rural pipe was 0.26 vol%. Although this is a significant amount relative to the gas quality specification, the effect on end-users of rural pipelines of low pressure is expected to be minimal. Nevertheless, purging some gas after a significant period of water ingress in a worst-case scenario would be a good preventive measure.

3.1.2.5 Conclusions

Based on the above analysis, the following conclusions can be made on impact of hydrogen quality on flame stability:

- Scenarios 2, 8, and 5 (nitrogen leak, oxygen leak, pipeline permeation) can all have a significant impact on the burning velocity of appliances without fuel/air control, the impact of the other scenarios was found to be minimal.
- Changes in burning velocity are more significant for lean-adjusted appliances than stoichiometric-adjusted appliances.
- Flame stability is highly dependent on burner design.
- With adequate, rapid fuel/air control the impact of contaminants on flame stability is expected to be minimal.
- Limits to the allowed reduction in burning velocity have not yet been experimentally determined for many future hydrogen appliance categories, whether industrial or residential. The point at which flame instability and lift-off occurs should be experimentally determined using field equipment and hydrogen with and without initial contaminants.
- It is at this point unclear what appliances would be used by customers attached to distribution networks. An inventory will have to be made to determine the respective tolerance to changes in Wobbe index of each appliance category.

3.1.3 Emissions and flue gas composition

3.1.3.1 Emissions and the flame temperature

Emissions are significantly affected by shifts in the excess air, the flame temperature and the fuel. Pure hydrogen does not generate CO or CO₂ emissions. It does, however, generate NO_x, the formation methods of which are described in HyDelta 2.0 WP9 in detail. In general, flame temperature increases - due to changes in the amount of excess air - will lead to the larger increase in NO_x formation (See Figure 3.7). Hydrogen burners are expected to be optimized and designed to burn with an excess of air. Therefore, more oxygen and nitrogen in the fuel will make the combustion more fuel-lean, due to the shift in equivalence ratio.

Figure 3.7: Calculated NOx emissions at various combustion temperatures. From [29].

This change in equivalence ratio directly affects the flame temperature as illustrated in the Table below for pure hydrogen and mixtures of hydrogen with contaminants from the different scenarios. The leaner the combustion (lower phi values), the lower the temperatures. Also, the fuel composition affects the flame temperature (and hence pollutant formation); for example, at phi=0.75 and 2 vol% ammonia in hydrogen the adiabatic flame temperature is lower as compared to the value for pure hydrogen, but 2 vol% nitrogen in hydrogen lowers the flame temperature even further.

Table 3.3: Thermodynamic data calculated using in-house tools. Note that Xylene was not available in the model and is therefore omitted from the table.

Scenario	Gas [vol%]	Adiabatic Flame T [K] $\phi = 0.75$	Adiabatic Flame T [K] $\phi = 1$	Δ Flame temperature $\phi = 0.75$	Δ Flame temperature $\phi = 1$
0	H ₂	2093	2381	0.00%	0.00%
2L	H ₂ + 2% N ₂	1921	2253	-8%	-5%
2H	H ₂ + 5% N ₂	1729	2059	-17%	-13%
8L	H ₂ + 2% O ₂	1896	2233	-9%	-6%
8H	H ₂ + 5% O ₂	1702	2018	-18%	-15%
9L	H ₂ + 2% NH ₃	2073	2354	-1%	-1%
9H	H ₂ + 5% NH ₃	1975	2296	-5%	-3%
7L	H ₂ + 3000 ppm benzene	2080	2379	-0.6%	-0.1%

7H	H ₂ + 6000 ppm benzene	2089	2377	-0.3%	-0.2%
5 (14 days)	H ₂ + permeate	2028	2336	-3%	-2%

Table 3.3, shows the effects of the contaminant scenarios on the flame temperature. In HyDelta 2.0 WP9 [29] it was described that flame temperature and NO emissions are strongly positively related.

For the calculations performed in this study, it can be concluded that for all contaminant scenarios the flame temperature is reduced, which is expecting to lead to a reduction in NO_x emissions, therefore there is no concern about NO_x emissions as compared to pure hydrogen. Other emissions, such as CO/CO₂ emissions can only occur when carbon atoms are present in the fuel, such as in scenarios 1 (THT has some carbon atoms) and 4 (benzene, toluene). To what extent a temporary CO/CO₂ increase is significant should be experimentally determined.

There are some caveats, however. It should be noted that, in the unlikely event appliances set to rich combustion ($\phi=1.5-3$) will experience an increase of adiabatic flame temperature and therefore an increase in emissions when the shift to the left occurs. However, it is unlikely that hydrogen burners would employ rich combustion due to NO_x emissions, as has been discussed in the flame stability discussion. Additionally, it is likely that burners utilizing oxy-hydrogen combustion, where pure oxygen is used instead of air, can see a significant increase in NO_x emissions when nitrogen-carrying contaminants (nitrogen gas or ammonia) enter the hydrogen used for combustion. Flame temperatures in oxy-hydrogen combustion are relatively high, and this will lead to an increase in NO_x formation (see Figure 2.9).

3.1.3.2 Water in the flue gas

Stoichiometric combustion of one mole of hydrogen with air produces ~27 mol% water and ~68 mol% nitrogen. The nitrogen is from the air supply itself and is not part of the combustion process, nor is it a flue gas of concern.

What can be of concern is the amount of water in the flue gas. The proportion of water, and the flue gas temperature are important criteria for equipment downstream of the combustion chamber such as chimneys and heat exchangers (or condensers) [30]. Equipment such as condensers are designed to extract the latent heat of condensation of flue gases and the geometry of these devices is dependent on the amount of flue gas and the flue gas temperature. Chimneys are designed to release harmful emissions at height but are not too tall to avoid gases condensing in the chimney. Again, the height of a chimney is dependent on the expected amount of water in the flue gas. Both chimney and heat exchanger design are also dependent on the flue gas flow rate. Lastly, an increase in water content (and thus water dew point) could cause early condensation in the downstream equipment which can increase corrosion [31].

Lastly, as discussed before, direct burners depend on a certain flue gas composition to transfer heat to the product which is part of their process. For example, a paper drying burner requires a specific amount of water in the flue gas for effective drying action. Changes in water content in the flue gas can significantly impact such processes. A bulk contamination lasting long enough could reduce the quality of a batch of product.

Table 3.4: Thermodynamic data calculated using DNV in-house tools. The flue gas flow rate is calculated from 1 Nm³/hr of 'fuel'. The water composition is calculated at constant pressure and enthalpy. Note that Xylene was not available in the

model and is therefore omitted from the table. $\varphi=1$ is between (brackets) and $\varphi=0.75$ is not. Flue gas flow rate is calculated for $\varphi=0.75$ only.

Scenario	Gas	Normalized flue gas flow rate w/o air control [Nm ³ /Nm ³ /hr]	Normalized flue gas flow rate with air control [Nm ³ /Nm ³ /hr]	Estimated H ₂ O in flue gas w/o air control [%]	Estimated H ₂ O in flue gas with air control [%]
0	H ₂	3.5		27 (32)	
2	H ₂ + 5% N ₂	4.2	3.3	20 (27)	27 (32)
8	H ₂ + 5% O ₂	4.2	3	20 (26)	29 (34)
9	H ₂ + 5% NH ₃	3.76	3.5	25 (27)	27 (32)
7	H ₂ + benzene	3.7	3.7	25 (31)	25 (31)
5	Permeation (14 days)	3.6	3.4	26 (32)	27 (32)

Table 3.4 shows the calculated flue gas properties for the various scenarios for two cases:

- Combustion with fuel/air control. In this case the amount of amount of air is adjusted to always achieve the set equivalence ratio of 0.75 or 1 using some form of feedback/feed forward control loop.
- Combustion without fuel/air control. In this case the equivalence ratio is allowed to drift based on the fuel composition and contaminants in the fuel.

As can be seen, fuel/air control significantly reduces the impact of the contaminants for all scenarios by reducing the effect of the shift in equivalence ratio caused by dilution. As with previous scenarios, the largest shift in equivalence ratio, as is the case in scenarios 2 and 8, has a noticeable impact on the flue gas flow rate (10-20% increase) and the amount of water (3-7% decrease). In both cases, chimney effectiveness and heat exchanger efficiency could be affected. However, contamination is only expected to last a short time. Therefore, increased corrosion or a long-term chimney/heat exchanger efficiency reduction is not expected.

3.1.3.3 Conclusions

Based on the above discussions, conclusions are:

- None of the scenarios have a significant detrimental effect on emissions. Carbon-based contaminants such as BTEX or odorants could cause some, temporary CO₂ emissions. However, the consequences of a short period of a low amount of CO₂ are expected to be low.
- For flame temperature and emissions, there is no notable mitigating effect of equivalence ratio on the impact of contaminants.
- Most contaminants will temporarily increase the flue gas flow rate and decrease or maintain the amount of water in the flue gas for both lean and stoichiometric combustion without air control.
- With air control the effects of contaminants are significantly reduced for emissions, flame temperature and flue gas flow rate and composition for all scenarios. This means that, when using fuel/air control, the impact on end-user equipment is expected to be minimal.

3.2 Feedstock

The largest current and future end-uses of hydrogen in the EU are ammonia (and derivatives) production through the Haber-Bosch process, sustainable fuels production (such as methanol) through the Fischer-Tropsch process, hydrocarbon refining and the steel industry [32], [33].

In this section the effect of contaminants released from the scenarios on feedstock processes will be discussed. As a general remark, industrial users requiring hydrogen to use as a chemical feedstock prefer the highest purity of hydrogen possible. 99.5% is too low for most industrial feedstock users, and they would have to install infrastructure to remove impurities [17]. The primary reasons for the requirement of pure hydrogen are (1) the prevention of catalyst poisoning and (2) process efficiency. These will be expanded upon below.

3.2.1 Catalyst poisoning

Catalyst poisoning is the major concern of industrial end-users (besides hydrogen costs) [17]. In both E-fuels production, through Fischer-Tropsch or derivative synthesis methods [34], and ammonia production, catalysts are typically used [35]. The hydrogenation of fats (for food production or biofuels production) will also be shortly discussed. Currently, the hydrogen used for these processes is of high quality (>99.97% is typical), requiring little to no purification.

For methanol production, the most typical catalysts used are Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃-based catalysts. These are vulnerable to sulphur-based components, such as those introduced in scenario 1 (THT is sulphur-based). Catalysts work by interacting chemically with gases, enhancing a desired reaction. The positive effect a catalyst has is based on its surface area, and therefore these materials are often used in grids, meshes or wools to maximise the surface of the material. Sulphur binds to the surface of some catalysts, slowly reducing the surface area over time, depending on the concentration. When bound to the surface, sulphur cannot be removed [34]. 10 ppm thiophene, which is chemically similar to THT, can poison these catalysts within weeks [34], [36]. Copper-based and aluminium-based catalysts can also be poisoned by HCl, through a process called sintering [37].

The production of ammonia, and ammonia derivatives such as fertilizers, is typically done with the Haber-Bosch process [38]. Typical ammonia catalysts are Ruthenium-based catalysts and iron-based catalysts [39]. These catalysts can be poisoned by oxygen and oxygen-containing components (H₂O, CO, CO₂) [38], in a similar mechanism to how sulphur poisons the catalysts for sustainable fuels production. For example, water at the 5-30 ppm level can significantly poison an iron catalyst at low temperatures, and 1.6 ppm oxygen has been reported to poison iron catalysts [40].

Hydrogen is also used in hydrotreating and hydrocracking processes in the oil refining industry in large quantities. Hydrogen is used the production of traditional fuels (e.g. diesel), but also in the production of more sustainable fuels such as HVO from used cooking oils (hydrogenated renewable diesel). In hydrotreatment processes, hydrogen is injected in a liquid or gaseous fuel to remove fuel-bound sulphur, oxygen and nitrogen. Bonds between carbon atoms and these contaminants are broken and the contaminants are bonded with hydrogen, which can then be separated from the fuel. Zeolite catalysts used in renewable diesel are vulnerable to sulphur compounds [41] as are aluminium-based catalyst used for hydrotreating diesel [42].

In the food industry, hydrogenation is used to produce solid fats (margarine, cake frosting) from liquid oils. Food grade hydrogen must be used in these processes [43]. In research, ultra-high purity (>99.999% H₂) is typically used [44]. Critical contaminants limits for margarine production specifically are sulphur < 200 ppm, inerts <0.2 vol%, moisture <0.1 vol% and CO < 30 ppm, which means the EZK

specification would not be sufficient [45]. The reasons provided for these limits are catalyst deactivation and process efficiency.

Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that industrial processes using hydrogen as feedstock can significantly be impacted by contaminants in hydrogen. Scenarios 1, 3 and 8 have to potential to release a large amount of catalyst poison to industrial end-users. However, the indicative specification already has several components (such as oxygen and CO/CO₂) above allowable levels for specific catalysts. This means that industrial end-users would have to create hydrogen purification infrastructure even without off-spec situations, as discussed in the introduction of this section. Therefore, the remaining question is whether the contaminants released in the off-spec scenarios could overwhelm the purification equipment installed. The ability of the purification equipment to remove the contaminants is highly dependent on [13]:

- Molecular properties of the contaminant (some molecules are more easily adsorbed than others).
- Size of the contamination (bulk contaminants can overwhelm filters/adsorber beds).
- Adsorbent material (some adsorbents are specific to contaminants, and many adsorbent materials are vulnerable to water).

3.2.2 Operational efficiency

Another consideration for industrial processes is operational efficiency. Large industrial facilities run on tight margins, and therefore small effects caused by contaminants can have large implications on the operation of the plant. Many processes are dependent on the partial pressure of hydrogen in the feedstock gas. For example, if the hydrogen purity is 99.5%, the partial pressure of hydrogen in a total gas pressure of 150 bar is 149.25 bar. Although the difference is small, the compressor responsible for maintaining the pressure in the process will need to continuously maintain the additional 0.75 bar of pressure of a non-functional gas, which reduces the operational efficiency of the plant.

Therefore, a large contaminant component of an inert gas like nitrogen, as is the case in scenario 1, can significantly reduce the operational efficiency of a process. However, the effect is unlikely to be permanent, and the off-specification gas is only expected to occur for a limited period of time. Therefore, the risk associated with operational losses is low.

3.3 Safety

This subsection will discuss any harm the contaminants (not the hydrogen by itself) can cause to people and the environment. The impact of the contaminants on (1) flammability and (2) toxicity to people will be discussed.

3.3.1 Flammability and explosion risk

Due to the low ignition energy which is required to ignite hydrogen, and the wide flammability limits, hydrogen can, in certain situation, pose an explosion hazard. A leak of oxygen, as described in Scenario 8 is an immediate risk to flammability. The lower flammability limit of hydrogen is very low compared to other gases. 4% hydrogen in oxygen is already a combustible mixture. Furthermore, 5% oxygen in hydrogen is a combustible mixture as well [46], [47], as depicted in the flammability diagram in Figure 3.8. Scenario 5 poses an immediate risk since the concentration of 5% oxygen nearly exceeds the flammability limit. Furthermore, mixing of gases may not be perfect, and pockets of oxygen may be locally present in the hydrogen.

Figure 3.8: Flammability diagram of hydrogen and air (oxygen and nitrogen) [46].

Besides oxygen, there is no expectation that any of the other contaminants described in the scenarios would affect either the leak rate of hydrogen or the flammability and ignition properties significantly. As an example, the LEL (lower explosive limit) of a hydrogen/ammonia mixture created in scenario 9 can be calculated using Le Chatelier’s principle and LEL data from IEC 60079 [48]:

$$LEL = \frac{1}{\sum \frac{x_i}{LEL_i}}$$

where 5% ammonia by volume with an LEL of 15% and hydrogen at 94% volume with an LEL of 4% leads to a total LEL of 4.15%, which is a negligible difference in practice when compared to pure hydrogen. Nitrogen and oxygen will dilute the fuel and reduce the LEL. To illustrate this, the LEL and UEL of leaked hydrogen and the bulk contaminants from scenarios 2, 5, 9, and 8 is calculated in Table 3.5. The table shows what the LEL of the leaked gas in a room of air would be. The UEL illustrates the upper limit, which is of concern when air enters a pipe/room filled with hydrogen.

Table 3.5: Recalculated flammability limits with bulk contaminants.

	H ₂	H ₂ + 5% N ₂	H ₂ + 5% NH ₃	H ₂ + 5% O ₂	H ₂ + permeate (14 days)
LEL	4%	4.21%	4.15%	4.21%	4.03%
UEL	75%	71.3%	69.2%	71.3%	74.5%

As can be seen in the table above, the effect of bulk contamination on flammability limits is insignificant. Permeation of pipes will not affect the LEL/UEL behaviour of hydrogen.

One of the primary explosion risks mitigators in gas infrastructure are leak detection (through detector systems) and odorization (using the human olfactory sense as a ‘detector’). Compliant with IEC standards, leak detection systems are set to signal operators at levels below the lower explosive limit. These thresholds are called alarm levels and are typically set at 10-20% (low alarm, signal alarm) and 25-40% (high alarm, evacuation alarm) of the 100% LEL level [49]. As described above, the contamination levels will be too low to impact the difference between the alarm levels and the LEL significantly.

DNV's research has found mine dust can contain significant amounts of black powder. When black powder is dry, there is a risk of spontaneous combustion (pyrophoric) due to the high content of iron sulphides, especially at elevated temperatures above 50 °C. Therefore, when taking black powder out of the gas system and into the air (such as in the case of swapping filters, or when doing maintenance in a pipe section) extra care should be taken after significant black powder contamination.

3.3.2 Toxicity

As can be seen toxic contaminants in high concentrations could impact the safety of persons in the case of a leak. The toxicity of the various contaminants in the scenarios will be outlined below.

However, specialized research is required to evaluate the impact of the toxicity. The toxicity of the scenarios 3, 4, 6 and 7 will be discussed. The other scenarios have no specific risk of toxicity to persons. Exposure data are attained from the SER (nl: *Social Economische Raad*) [50] and are generally TGG (Dutch term for temporary weighted average) values unless otherwise specified.

Scenario 3 (short-circuit near PVC pipeline): In a short circuit near a PVC pipeline, the burning of the plastic can result in formaldehyde and hydrochloric acid in the hydrogen at 139-447 mg/m³(locally). The 8-hour limit for formaldehyde is 0.15 mg/m³ and 0.5 mg/m³ for 15 minutes and the limit for hydrochloric acid is 8 mg/m³ for 8 hours and 15 mg/m³ for 15 minutes. The highest concentrations are present near the fire in the combustion products.

Scenario 7 (BTEX release through LOHC failure): Benzene is a carcinogen and toxic in low concentrations, whereas xylene and its isomers are not proven to be carcinogens. The 8-hour exposure values are 0.7 mg/m³ (~1 ppm) for benzene and 210 mg/m³ for xylene. Benzene vapour is colourless.

Scenario 8 (Ammonia cracker failure): Ammonia is a toxic substance. The 8-hour exposure limit is 14 mg/m³ (22 ppm) and the 15-minute limit is 36 mg/m³ (50 ppm). Depending on atmospheric and gas conditions, ammonia can be colourless or visible as a mist.

Scenario 4 (mine dust release): Mine dust (black powder) has several toxic properties [51]:

- Cyanide containing components can react with water to form hydrogen cyanide, a highly toxic substance. The maximum exposure (MAC) limit is 1 mg/m³ for 8 hours and 10 mg/m³ for 10 minutes.
- Cartridge filters exposed to black powder can contain mercury. Mercury vapours can be released from these filters even at room temperature. The maximum exposure limit is 0.05 mg/m³ for 8 hours and 0.5 mg/m³ for 10 minutes.
- Lead (Pb-210) and Radon (Ra-226, 228 and 229) emit some background radiation in black powder, but this is not untypical for gas infrastructure filters.
- When black powder/mine dust is on fire (or smouldering) additional toxic substances such as sulphur (dioxide and trioxide) and mercury oxide can be released.

3.3.3 Odorization

In terms of odorization, there are two events; (1) a hydrogen leak with one of the contaminants when the hydrogen is not odorized, a (2) leak with one of the contaminants when the gas is odorized.

Release of contaminated hydrogen without odorization:

In this event, scenarios 3, 7 and 9 can all result in a release of toxic gases (BTEX, hydrogen chloride and ammonia respectively) without odorization. All these gases have some form of odor, but they differ widely. According to the National Center for Biotechnology Information [52] benzene and xylene have a sweet odor, HCl has a sharp, pungent odor and ammonia has a 'strong' odor. None of

these substances have a sulfur-like odor that would indicate a gas leak, meaning people would not be warned to the fact that a leak is the cause of the odor.

Release of contaminated hydrogen with odorization:

In this event, the odorant should warn people of a gas leak. However, it is unclear whether the odors of the toxic gases would mask the odorant or whether the odorant would mask the odors of the toxic gases. This can only be determined experimentally. Nor is it possible to determine whether toxic concentrations of these gases would accumulate in a space without warning without a specific study on the topic.

Concluding, many interactions are possible between odorants and contaminants in Scenarios 1, 3, 7 and 9. However, interactions between these contaminants are not fully understood and this is therefore recognized as a knowledge gap. However, note that the chance that a hydrogen leak occurs during one of the contamination scenarios is relatively small compared to a leak of hydrogen without contaminants. Regardless, the consequences can be significant.

3.4 Operational end-users

The final impact which is discussed is the impact on the operational end-users (the distributors). This refers to components owned and maintained by distributors. To do so, the impact of the contaminants on several components which are expected in a future hydrogen network will be analysed. These components are:

- (1) Flow meters (turbine, ultrasonic).
- (2) Filters for dust and particulates.
- (3) Compressors.

3.4.1 Flow meters

The flow meter types which are the most expected in hydrogen infrastructure are turbine meters, Coriolis meters and ultrasonic meters. An in-depth analysis of each of these meters is beyond the scope of this report. However, some considerations of the impact of hydrogen contaminants will be discussed below.

Ultrasonic meters:

Ultrasonic meters measure flow velocity through differences in down-stream and up-stream path travel times through the flow. Travel time is determined by the speed of sound (SoS) of a gas. The SoS of hydrogen is significantly higher (4-5x) than any other gas, with the exception of helium, as can be seen in Table 3.6.

Table 3.6: Speed of sound of various gases at 27-30°C [53].

Gas	H ₂ (27 °C)	N ₂ (29 °C)	NH ₃ (30 °C)	O ₂ (27 °C)	CH ₄ (27 °C)
SoS [m/s]	1320	354	440	330	450

Because of this large difference, a nitrogen contamination of 5% could lower the total speed of sound of the gas by a proportional amount if proportional mixing rules are used ($0.95 \cdot H_2 + 0.05 \cdot N_2 \approx 1270$ m/s). However, speed of sound is dependent on the density and compressibility of a gas, which does not necessarily behave by proportional mixing laws. The SoS can be calculated from a known composition in commonly used models such as those defined by AGA-8-2017 and GERG-2008 [54], [55]. Furthermore, ultrasonic meters can also measure the SoS of the medium they are measuring and could therefore compensate for any contamination to a degree, by estimating the hydrogen

concentration [55], [56]. However, care should be taken with AGA and GERG models if they exceed validated compositional parameters [57].

Unfortunately, experimental information on the accuracy of ultrasonic meters with hydrogen contaminants is limited. A 2024 paper describes the effects of 1% nitrogen and 1% methane on hydrogen measurement for an Emerson FLUXUS clamp-on ultrasonic meter. For these contaminants, the measurement error was well within specification, indicating that the contaminants did not significantly impact the accuracy [58]. However, it is not expected that typical ultrasonic meters calibrated for pure hydrogen are programmed to recognize and compensate for large contaminations. Therefore, discussions should be had with manufacturers on the accuracy of their meters in scenarios such as 2, 8 and 9 where a large contamination can affect the SoS of the gas.

Turbine meters:

Turbine meters consist of a freely spinning turbine which is rotated by the kinetic energy impacted by the gas on the blades. A turbine meter measures flow velocity by converting the rotational speed of the rotor to flow velocity using proportionality. A critical factor for the proportionality of the flow velocity of a gas to the rotation speed of the turbine blades is the dynamic pressure, which is a function of the flow velocity u and the density ρ of the gas:

$$P_{dyn} = \frac{\rho u^2}{2}.$$

As can be seen in the equation above, flow velocity is the major component in the dynamic pressure equation since it is a squared term, but density is also proportional to the pressure. Therefore, changes in density by contaminants will significantly impact the dynamic pressure of the gas on the turbine blades and thus affecting the repeatability and linearity of the meter [59]. However, flow velocity has a far greater impact. Therefore, in practice, turbine meters are designed for an operating range of various Reynolds numbers, which is a function of viscosity, density and flow velocity. Calibration on the basis of Reynolds number can reduce uncertainty by variation in density and flow velocity [60], and this is recommended when contaminants are expected. It should be noted that some the rangeability (the range between the minimum and maximum flow rates which can be measured accurately) can be affected by changes in gas density.

A more significant threat to rotating components such as turbine meters are particles, which are a contaminant introduced in scenario 4. At lower flow rates, the effect of bearing friction becomes more dominant, since the difference between the force to overcome bearing friction and rotational force by the flow is lower. The friction force of the bearings in turbine meters can be increased substantially if fine particles become lodged in the bearing clearance [59], [61]. This will result in an underestimation of the flow rate [62] as seen in Figure 3.9.

Dirt accumulated in bearings slows down a turbine meter, therefore results in underestimated flow volume.

Figure 3.9: Error caused by damage to bearings. From [62].

Coriolis meters:

In Coriolis flow meters two u-shaped pipe sections are vibrated by two motors. Sensors at the inlet and outlet of the vibrating system detect the local frequency. The Coriolis force acted upon the fluid will create a twist in the elbow tubing, which will induce a phase frequency shift in the oscillating system. This phase shift is then measured, and the mass flow and density of the fluid can be determined based on this shift.

It is not the expectation that Coriolis meters will be significantly impacted by contaminants in hydrogen. Coriolis meters for hydrogen service are typically calibrated with water, which is a high-density liquid compared to hydrogen or the other contaminants. The accuracy of these systems does not depend on the molecular weight of the gas which passes through the meter [63]. Furthermore, meters calibrated with water designed for hydrogen metering remain accurate for a variety of other gases [64]. Therefore, it is the expectation that the meter will remain accurate in terms of total mass flow when contaminants are introduced. However, only the total mass flow will remain accurate. Coriolis meters do not discriminate between the contaminant and bulk gas flow.

3.4.2 Filters for dust and particulates

Filters are components in natural gas infrastructure which collect particulates and dust and liquids at certain points in the network (typically at GOS and M+R stations and before compression). Several types of filters are generally used such as cartridge filters (nl: *filterkaarsen*), coalescing filters, dust filters and cyclone filters. There is no expectation that these systems would be different for hydrogen systems.

Dust filters become saturated over time. When a filter gets saturated, the pressuredrop increases. Measuring the pressure drop over a pipe section with a filter indicates the remaining operational life of the filter itself [65]. The rate at which a filter becomes saturated is dependent on the grain of the filter, the size of the particles in the gas, the number of particles in the gas and the flow velocity.

Scenario 4 describes a sudden increase in mine dust in hydrogen. At equal velocity, this will increase the rate at which filters saturate. Mine dust has been a problem for filters the natural gas network, especially in the south of the Netherlands. Mine dust can compose of rust, sand, but also cyanide and cyanide compounds. DNV's research has found mine dust can consist of very small particles, and up to 33% can be smaller than 3 μm , which is smaller than typical cartridge filters (3 μm). At GOS stations, 5 μm filters are sometimes used, leading almost 50% of mine dust passing through the filter.

Currently, the EZK specification does not include a quantifiable measure for dust and particulates, only stating that:

“Shall not contain solid, liquid or gaseous material that might interfere with the integrity or operation of pipes or any gas appliance”.

Even though the impact of large amounts of dust being released can result in filter saturation, leading to increased pressure drop over, for example, GOS. Eventually, breakthrough of the dust through the filter can result in dust and particulates ending up at end-users. As discussed in the previous section on flow meters, dust and particulates are of concern to any rotating and moving machinery such as turbines and compressors. However, many end-users operating rotating machinery such as power turbines will have filters installed. The result is that these filters will saturate faster.

3.4.3 Compressors

If the compressor has rotating machinery, the same considerations as stated above apply regarding Scenario 4 (mine dust). Furthermore, changes in gas properties affect the required power for compression, including molecular, compressibility of the gas and the real isentropic expansion factor (ratio of specific heat at constant pressure and volume, $C_p/C_v = \kappa$) [66]. These effects will be illustrated with an example; the underlying equations and calculations are presented in the Appendix.

In the example, the changes in power requirement for an increase in pressure from atmospheric to 10 bar are calculated at equal energy transport capacity [MJ/s]. Initial conditions (without contamination) are shown in the Table below:

Table 3.7: Initial conditions for the compressor power calculations.

Property	Inlet	Outlet
Gas	100% Hydrogen, pure	
Pressure	1.01325 bar (atmospheric)	10 bar
Volumetric flow	2000 m ³ /hr	~200 m ³ /hr
Energy flow	6.7 MJ/s (kept constant)	
Nominal required power	243 kW (72% efficiency)	

Figure 3.10: Calculated compressor power requirements at equal energy flow of 6.7 MJ/s at an inlet inflow of 2000 m³/hr.

Based on the initial conditions presented in Table 3.7, the calculated power requirements are shown in Figure 3.10: Calculated compressor power requirements at equal energy flow of 6.7 MJ/s at an inlet inflow of 2000 m³/hr. Figure 3.10. As can be seen, both nitrogen and oxygen introduce a 5% increase in required power. Ammonia reduces the required power due to the energy density and thermodynamic properties of ammonia itself. Ammonia has a lower specific heat ratio, and a higher molecular weight. However, note that regulations such as those proposed by EASEE-gas [67] might only count the hydrogen molecules in a hydrogen composition as having any legal energetic value, not other combustibles. Therefore, the ‘useful’ energy capacity will be reduced with ammonia in hydrogen.

As a final note for compressors, they are often powered by an internal combustion engine, called a prime mover. The same considerations for heating value and Wobbe index described in the previous subchapter for internal combustion engines (CHP) extend to prime movers.

3.4.4 Materials

A final consideration for operational end-users is the effect of contamination on materials. As a general rule, most contamination scenarios can already occur in existing natural gas pipelines, and the switch to hydrogen infrastructure does not significantly alter the impact on materials and components.

For example, hydrochloric acid released as a result of a short circuit in a PVC pipeline can have a significant impact on gas meters and other pipe components (Scenario 3) by rapidly accelerating corrosion of metallic parts [68]. The effect of hydrochloric acid on polymeric materials is more limited [69], [70]. Sulphur containing components can somewhat affect steel components [70]. Ammonia has relatively little impact on materials. However, all these corrosive effects can already occur in natural gas infrastructure and therefore require no additional consideration in this report.

The largest consideration is the ingress of water, since water generally accelerates the corrosion of materials by substances such as sulphur, hydrogen sulphide and oxygen [70]. However, the amount of water ingress for hydrogen infrastructure is not expected to be different than that for hydrogen gas [11].

3.4.5 Interaction black powder and hydrogen

HyDelta 3.0 WP 1B D1b.1 - "Pipeline Contamination" investigated and summarized the known the chemical and physical interaction of black powder and hydrogen [71] in subsection 4.11. In this section, it is discussed that hydrogen is relatively inert without high temperatures or a catalyst such as platinum or palladium being present. These two materials are not often present in gas networks. Iron and iron oxides can sometimes act as a catalyst as well and can be present in a network.

Several reactions between hydrogen and components in black powder and mine dust are discussed in the HyDelta work and previous work by DNV on the subject [72], including:

- Iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) to iron and water, taking place at 1000 °C
- Mercury sulphide (HgS), to mercury and hydrogen sulphide, taking place at 340 °C
- Sulphur (S), to hydrogen sulphide, at 340 °C
- Carbon (C), to methane at 400 °C, 300 bar and with a catalyst

As can be seen most of these reactions require a high temperature or a catalyst and are therefore not expected during normal operation. Hydrogen is not very reactive at room temperature. It was also concluded that iron sulphides ($\text{Fe}_{(1+x)}\text{S}$, FeS , Fe_3S_4 , $\text{Fe}_{(1-x)}\text{S}$ and two forms of FeS_2), iron carbonates and iron oxide (Fe_3O_4) found in mine dust/black powder do not react with hydrogen. For the studies components listed above, no reaction is expected between black powder and hydrogen.

The formation of hydrogen cyanide (HCN) from cyanide (CN^-) occurs in water, so if there is no additional water (compared to natural gas) there is no increased risk for reaction of hydrogen and cyanide [72]. The maximum concentration found was up to 20 mg/kg CN/HCN with a normal variation between 0 and 5 mg/kg in the filter residue. Hydrogen is expected to transport the cyanide along with the black powder/mine dust just like natural gas does, without any specific interaction that would affect the Wobbe index or purity level specification.

Furthermore, the normal concentration of black powder is relatively low to the total bulk gas. However, exact concentrations per gas volume are unknown (only the filter concentration is known). Therefore, the possible influence of black powder on the Wobbe index or purity level is expected to be minimal. Only in the presence of water some reaction can occur with cyanide, but this is independent of whether the gas is hydrogen or natural gas. Furthermore, cyanide is not included in the *Ministriële Regeling gaskwaliteit* nor in the proposed hydrogen network specification.

3.5 Note on ammonia

Scenario 9 describes an error in an ammonia cracker. Ammonia is a substance which is gaseous under ambient conditions (atmospheric pressure and 20 °C) but is on the edge of becoming liquid with slightly increased pressure or a reduction in temperature, when it is in pure form (anhydrous ammonia). Fortunately, even with large amounts of ammonia in hydrogen, the gas is not expected to become liquid under operating conditions typical for distribution. This will be discussed below.

Figure 3.11: Phase envelope of a 95/5 vol% H₂/NH₃ mixture. Calculated using DNV's tool GasVLE.

As can be seen in Figure 3.11, the dew line (temperature/pressure line at which liquid forms) is at extreme cold temperatures (-120 < -60) for 5% ammonia in hydrogen at distribution pressures. This is due to the low partial pressure of ammonia, and the very low dew line of pure hydrogen. Therefore, it can be concluded that no two-phase behaviour is expected to occur at distribution pressure even at the extreme contamination scenario as presented in Scenario 6.

4. Conclusion: Realistic hydrogen specification in distribution networks.

Based on the above analysis, conclusions can be made for production errors and operational/distribution errors in the context of the EZK-specification and the ability to guarantee it throughout the network. Two of the described operational/distribution errors:

- Fire or heat buildup near PVC pipelines (scenario 3)
- Mine dust release (scenario 4)

can already occur in natural gas infrastructure and have no specific interaction with hydrogen when they happen in hydrogen infrastructure. The same mitigating measures/effects apply for the new infrastructure as they do for natural gas.

Fire near PVC pipelines is only expected to have local effects, and there is no significant expectation that feedstock industry would be found downstream of this fire. Although the resulting gases are toxic, this is true of any plastic fire and has no specific, additional considerations for hydrogen infrastructure as opposed to natural gas infrastructure. Therefore, the EZK-specification remains adequate.

The same conclusion can be drawn for the mine dust release scenario. Considerations made for mine dust in natural gas infrastructure are the same as those for hydrogen infrastructure. The reaction mechanisms with components of mine dust were analysed for any special interaction with hydrogen, and none were found based on available information. One minor risk would be a possibly increased flow velocity increasing the saturation rate of filters, but this does not pose a significant risk if filters are maintained regularly. Including a technical limit for particulates specifically for the RDN requires further research and is dependent on whether this is currently required for natural gas infrastructure or not.

Some contaminant scenarios can have significant impact on the feedstock industry, through the deactivation/poisoning of catalysts. These include any sulphur-based contaminations, a plastic fire and the introduction of oxygen to the net. Of the sulphur-based contaminations, it is highly unlikely that the desorption of THT in low pressure pipelines can significantly affect the feedstock industry, since those industries would not be connected to the network at these low pressures where desorption takes place. An over-injection of odorant could affect the industry however, and the suitability of sulphur-removing systems at feedstock industries should be prepared for this impactful, albeit unlikely, event.

The introduction of nitrogen (either through production error or permeation) can have direct implications for the specification. The EZK-specification limits nitrogen to 0.5%. If this amount of nitrogen is present in the hydrogen passed down from the high-pressure network, permeation or any possible contaminant from production will push the hydrogen in the distribution network off specification due to the 0.5% inert component limit. The same can be concluded for air inleak, desorption of hydrocarbons and odorants and water, especially at low pressures and in summer. Therefore, it can be concluded that low-pressure networks might not be able to maintain the specification during normal operation.

However, the Wobbe limit in the specification is slightly more relaxed (allowing 0.7% N₂) compared to the purity limit of 0.5% nitrogen allowable. This indicates at least some increased tolerance for combustion equipment dependent on the Wobbe index. Furthermore, available literature, such as research projects and the previous iteration of the EZK-specification, indicate that the Wobbe tolerance of both residential and industrial appliances could be significantly broader (4 MJ/m³) allowing up to 1% nitrogen to be present in the system.

This opens the avenue to relaxing the hydrogen purity at a certain point in the network where only end users with appliances tolerant to a broader Wobbe index are present. In the case of a residential network, this could be, for example, below 1 bar (but this could also be, 4 bar if there are, for example, no feedstock industries below 4 bar), where a relaxed version of the EZK-specification begins. Coincidentally, this is also where permeation rates are the highest, and thus where the highest change of falling below the EZK-specification occurs. However, this solution would only be possible if the following conditions are met:

- It should be ensured that a relaxed EZK-specification cannot be boosted back up to the high-pressure network (or designate this part of the system as end-use only)
- The flame stability of all appliances within the relaxed Wobbe/hydrogen purity range should be experimentally validated
- The change in Wobbe index should be rate-limited (not change too fast)
- Oxygen contamination should always be limited to a safe level of at most 10% LEL/UEL (for example 0.2%)

By including these considerations, the hydrogen specification for dedicated hydrogen networks on transmission (HTL) and distribution (RDN) level could be:

Property		Value
Wobbe index	HTL and RDN > 1 bar	45.99 - 48.35 MJ/(n)m ³ [25/0 °C]
	RDN < 1 bar	44.35 - 48.35 MJ/(n)m ³ [25/0 °C] ΔWI ≤ 0.5 MJ/m ³ ·minute [25/0 °C]
Hydrogen Purity	HTL and RDN > 1 bar	≥ 99.5 mol%
	RDN < 1 bar	>98 mol%
Inert gases	HTL and RDN > 1 bar	≤ 0.5 mol-%
	RDN < 1 bar	No limitation as long as Wobbe limit is met
Total hydrocarbons	HTL and RDN > 1 bar	≤ 0.5 mol-%
	RDN < 1 bar	No limitation as long as Wobbe limit is met
Oxygen	HTL and RDN > 1 bar	≤ 10 ppm
	RDN < 1 bar	≤ 0.2 mol-%

By introducing the above alteration into the future hydrogen counterpart of the Ministeriële *Regeling gaskwaliteit* would allow hydrogen specifications to be met in low pressure parts of the network.

5. Recommendations

Based on the current work, the following recommendations can be made:

- Identify commercial and residential combustion end-use equipment which will be used in the new hydrogen network.
- Test the identified equipment for combustion stability beyond the EZK-specification set limits including:
 - Establishing a tolerable Wobbe Index range, and rate of change.
 - Inert gas tolerability.
 - Water ingress tolerability.
 - Flame stability.
- Identify industrial end users and inventory the following:
 - Required connection pressure.
 - Required contaminant limits.
 - Gas purification equipment on-site.

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Appendix

Table 0.1 shows the constants for all bulk contaminant scenarios. The constants have been calculated using equations of state in Cantera. Furthermore, Table 0.1 shows the adiabatic compression head H [j/g] with a pressure inlet of 101.325 kPa (atmospheric) to 1,000.000 kPa (10 bar) using the equation:

$$H_c = \frac{\kappa \cdot Z \cdot R \cdot T_{in}}{\kappa - 1 \cdot MW} \times \left[\frac{p_{out}^{(\kappa-1)/\kappa}}{p_{in}} - 1 \right]$$

where κ is the isentropic expansion factor, Z is the compressibility R is 8.314 [J·K⁻¹·mol⁻¹], T_{in} is inlet temperature in [K], MW is the mean molecular weight of the gas in [g/mol] and p are the in and outlet pressures in [Pa]. Adiabatic compression head provides an indication of the required energy in J to compress one gram of a gas. Multiplying this equation with the mass flow Q [kg/hr], the energy per unit of mass and an efficiency factor calculates the required compressor power. The chosen energy capacity was based on a hydrogen flow of 2000 m³/hr at the atmospheric side of the compressor resulting in an energy capacity of 6.7 MJ/s.

Table 0.1: Calculation of compressor power and adiabatic head. Power requirement is calculated at equal volumetric flow at 2000 Nm³/hr with a compressor efficiency of 0.72.

Scenario	Atmospheric inlet gas, 288.15 K, 101325 Pa	Mean molecular	κ	H_c [j/g]	Energy density	Mass flow [kg/hr]	Power Required [kW]
o							

		weight [g/mol]			(Gross) [MJ/kg]		
0	H ₂	2.016	1.405	3855	141.79	170.52	253.65
6	H ₂ + 5% NH ₃	2.7667	1.400	2799	105.07	230.12	248.52
2	H ₂ + 5% N ₂	3.3159	1.405	2344	81.89	295.24	266.96
5	H ₂ + 5% O ₂	3.5151	1.406	2212	77.25	312.9	267.06